

NEANIAS
**Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere,
Underwater and Space Challenges**

Deliverable Report

**Deliverable:D2.2 - Underwater Research Services Report on
Requirements and Specifications**

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D2.2 - Underwater Research Services Report on Requirements and Specifications

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NEANIAS is a project that comprehensively addresses the 'Prototyping New Innovative Services' challenge set out in the 'Roadmap for EOSC' foreseen actions. It drives the co-design, delivery, and integration into EOSC of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. In each sector it engages a diverse set of research and business groups, practices, and technologies and will not only address its community-specific needs but will also enable the transition of the respective community to the EOSC concept and Open Science principles. NEANIAS provides its communities with plentiful resource access, collaboration instruments, and interdisciplinary research mechanisms, which will amplify and broaden each community's research and knowledge generation activities. NEANIAS delivers a rich set of services, designed to be flexible and extensible, able to accommodate the needs of communities beyond their original definition and to adapt to neighbouring cases, fostering reproducibility and re-usability. NEANIAS identifies promising, cutting-edge business cases across several user communities and lays out several concrete exploitation opportunities.

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Abstract

The objective of deliverable D2.2 is to report on the final set of service requirements, software specifications and upcoming development plan of the foreseen Underwater Research Services. These three services aiming at providing operational cloud solution for: **i) Bathymetry mapping from acoustic data service implementation (U1), ii) Seafloor Mosaicking from Optical Data (U2), and iii) Seabed Classification from Multispectral, Multibeam Data (U3)**. This document reports on Underwater end-user communities, involved datasets and products as well as the current status of employed software and services. Then it presents results from the service requirement validation based on current software releases. While the U1 service has not yet completed the 2nd release (due on 31st October 2021), a series of validation trials and dissemination actions involving end-users of all the underwater sector on the 2nd release of U2 and U3 services have resulted in working towards the final set of the end-users requirements and software specifications, marking a considerable progress towards the employment of novel, user-friendly, automatised and efficient novel EOSC underwater services to be further developed at the 3rd release. This was the result of a very intense collaboration between the developers, the technical team, the end-users communities of NEANIAS as well as external advisors of NEANIAS. As the U1 service was not ready at the due date of the 2nd release no U1 service end-user validation trials and dissemination actions have been performed. Hence at the time the U2 and U3 services performed the end-user trials no specification and requirements could be retrieved from the end-users to improve the U1 service based on the end-user feedback.

1. Introduction

1.1. Context

The WP2 “Underwater Services” involves three out of nine thematic services of the NEANIAS project (<https://www.neanias.eu/>). The overall common goal is the development of thematic cloud services which support the analysis and data management of a large diversity of tasks within the fields of underwater, atmosphere and space research. Easy to handle, fair to use and platform independent services.

1.2. Contents and Rationale

This deliverable, D2.2, is a report containing the details of the developed and validated Underwater Services, delivered in the 2nd release and listed in the deliverables D2.5 “Underwater Thematic Services Release #2 (U1/U2/U3)” and D2.6 “Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services (Release #2)”.

Preliminary documents have been prepared for each of the services (U1, U2, U3), within the NEANIAS WP2 workspace, collecting the required datasets for service validation, software underlying technologies as well as collecting all possible contributions as Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to evaluate their success.

1.3. Changes from previous release report

The initial content and main structure of this document has been given by D2.1 reporting the initial user requirements, service specifications and software development plan. A new chapter, Chapter 3, has been added to report the methodology employed to validate the initial set of requirements, evaluating to what extent NEANIAS services adapt to the evolving nature of underwater research by conducting a targeted survey. All chapters have been updated according to the maturity level reached by the underwater services and the results of the services assessment, validation and feedback given by the service users. Note that as the U1 service has not been validated by end-users at this time the changes from the previous release report do not include any U1 updates.

1.4. Structure of the document

The deliverable is structured in five sections (chapters), being the first one responsible for introducing the report, briefly mentioning its content and how it is structured. Chapter 2 describes the Underwater end-user communities (section 2.1), their datasets and products (section 2.2), the current state of the software and services employed (section 2.3) and the requirements (section 2.4), finally, the user requirements level of priority, value and acceptance (section 2.5), while Chapter 3 details the results of targeted trials and dissemination activities we have conducted to validate the initial set of requirements, described in Chapter 2, evaluating to what extent NEANIAS services adapt to the evolving nature of Underwater research and to take the pulse of the community toward enhancing the Underwater services co-design and specifications. Chapter 4 presents the current status of the services and highlight the technical software specifications to address the requirements. Finally, Chapter 5 outlines the conclusions.

2. User Requirements for the Underwater Services

2.1. Underwater End-user Communities

Knowing the depth, shape and type of the seafloor (bathymetry) is fundamental for understanding ocean circulation, tides, tsunami forecasting, fishing resources, sediment transport, bottom currents, environmental change, underwater geohazards, submerged remains of underwater cultural heritage, such as shipwrecks, artefacts and sunken cities, topography of archaeological sites, cable and pipeline routing, mineral extraction, oil and gas exploration and development, infrastructure construction and maintenance and much more.

Underwater Community	Brief Description
Archaeologists	Reconnaissance, optical documentation of underwater sites, mapping of sea-floor topography of archaeological sites, monitoring for protection (natural and anthropogenic hazards) and management, measure objects and artefacts on the site, geo-location of shipwrecks
Geologists/Biologists/Oceanographers/Environmental Scientists	Submarine geohazards, habitat mapping, marine ecosystems, marine geomorphology, seabed classification/geological maps, offshore structural geology & tectonics interpretations;
Oil & gas engineers	Pipeline planning (geomorphology), habitat mapping & marine ecosystems interactions, structural geology/tectonics (fault detection, risk assessment)
Renewable energy planners	Seabed/soil/ground classification, risk assessment (faults, geohazard potential)
Robotics	Mosaicking and 3D reconstruction of the surveyed area, global alignment of on-board navigation with image registration for improved navigation, path planning
Civil engineering	Potential of submarine geohazards, seabed classification with respect to underwater constructions.
Computer vision/ machine learning software engineers	Mosaicking and/or 3D reconstruction of the scene seen by a moving camera, mapping, annotation and/or detection and classification of underwater elements
Insurance	Risk assessment, subaquatic geohazard potential

Table 1 Underwater end-user communities

Below, the most represented groups of end-user communities within NEANIAS WP2 are analysed in detail to contextualize the deliverable main themes focused on the Underwater research data, products and software toward the definition of the user requirements to guide the NEANIAS services developments.

2.1.1. Archaeologists

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More than estimated (and still triggering human imagination), a large part of our cultural heritage, is today submerged, consisting namely of ancient submerged cities, coastal areas and shipwrecks of all centuries. The 2001 UNESCO Convention on the Protection of underwater cultural heritage (UCH) promotes in situ conservation as the first option (<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000126065>). Therefore, digital surveying, mapping and 3D modelling are key tools for documenting, visualizing, monitoring and assessing the preservation state of the UCH. They are also essential for raising public awareness and promoting the diffusion of information between the different scientific communities, as well as the public (Menna et al. 2018).

As a result, the archaeological community will use the three services proposed by NEANIAS:

- **Sea-floor mosaicking (3D photogrammetry)**
- **Seabed classification and Bathymetry**
- **Applied interdisciplinary methodologies**

In order to better process interdisciplinary databases from 3D digital surveying and modelling techniques, with the following main objectives:

- **1. Reconnaissance.** Identifying archaeological sites, such as shipwrecks, submerged cities, artefacts, etc.
- **2. Documentation.** Detailed archaeological documentation recording of underwater cultural heritage (UCH) as a means for accumulated knowledge. Especially in the case of underwater or coastal excavation, the process of excavating is irreversibly destructive. Therefore, detailed documentation of every step is the essential requirement of any serious and thorough systematic scientific work.
- **3. Enhanced interpretation and analysis**
- **4. Monitoring for protection and management**
 - 4a. during archaeological excavation (documenting different phases of the excavation process)
 - 4b. in case of imminent or long-term natural or anthropogenic threat
 - 4c. for developing preservation strategies and management policies for protection.
- **5. Dissemination** for the wider public. This type of 3D documentation is used for sharing the results and facilitating dissemination strategies, such as 3D modelling, directly used in application of virtual and augmented reality, serious games etc. targeting public of all ages.

Sea-floor mosaicking (3D photogrammetry)

3D photogrammetric plans are part of the graphic representations of sites (under survey or excavation), among architectural plans and drawings, aerial (drone) and underwater photographs.

3D photogrammetric documentation provides a benefit to the archaeological scientific community:

- a-** It offers a 3D representation of the site, difficult to easily comprehend in the underwater environment (Drap 2012).
- b-** It offers unlimited possibilities to test different hypotheses via hypothetical reconstructions (of submerged cities, harbours, ships) and modelling that should be driven by expert archaeological knowledge.
- c-** Facilitates dissemination strategies for the wider public (including non-divers) enabling a comprehensive view of how the ancient world may have looked like, thus raising public awareness and active engagement. Moreover, digital products are the base for Virtual and Augmented reality

applications, etc. Often, they are used to produce virtual tours of the modelled areas for the public, especially the non-divers, so that they gain an appreciation of the underwater cultural heritage.

Parameters of Underwater photogrammetry

Methodologically, the objective of underwater photogrammetry is to obtain a 3D geometrical modelling product from the oriented photos of the recorded sites and/or artifacts.

Underwater photogrammetry presents a series of parameters to be taken into account, in order to achieve a high level of accuracy, such as the refraction of the dioptré water glass and constraints of the underwater medium (turbidity of the water, presence of suspended particles, etc.). Methodologically, these specific constraints force the operators to work on large scales, close to the objects (between 0.5 and 2 to 3 meters, depending on the water quality). Moreover, the photographs have to be taken with an important overlap. The key factor of this method is redundancy: each point of measured space must be seen in at least three photographs. The calibration of the cameras and their housing is also essential.

In recent years, a series of shipwrecks, amphorae cargos, underwater sites and submerged UCH monuments have been documented by advancing experimental techniques, as well as the available software to underwater community (Seinturier et al. 2004; Murai et al. 1988; Drap 2012; Drap 2012b; McCarthy-Benjamin 2014; McCathy et al. 2018; Diamanti-Vlachaki 2015; Zhukovsky et al. 2013). In some cases, archaeological remains were half-submerged, a condition that required a special treatment of the submerged and the emerged part in the photogrammetric documentation (Menna et al. 2015).

For selected case-studies in underwater archaeological research and the specific requirements underwater archaeologists are expecting from software development, see 2.2.1.

Seabed classification and Bathymetry

Archaeologists are using marine geoscience technologies and tools for the location, mapping and interpretation of submerged and coastal sites. In all cases, archaeologists are end-users of the geoscientific marine prospections (geological, oceanographic, biological, and environmental) (for the state of art and application in archaeological 3D recording and mapping - see Menna et al 2018).

- Objectives:

a. - Palaeoshoreline reconstruction- coastal palaeoenvironmental study - sea-bed topography

Landscape reconstruction, reconstruction of the relative sea-level change for different periods of times, coastline reconstruction: These are essential steps for the analysis and interpretation of submerged maritime landscapes and the study of underwater topography of submerged sites. Geological and anthropogenic factors have altered drastically past landscapes, that cannot be comprehended, if their extend and physical development is not clarified by geomorphological reconstruction (Baily et al. 2007; Baily 2009; Flemming et al. 2014; Mahon et al. 2011; Henderson et al. 2013; Missiaen et al. 2017; Nikolakopoulos et al. 2019). Moreover, knowledge of underwater topography is essential for the understanding of the organization and distribution of archaeological sites along and in water bodies (Doneus et al. 2015).

b. - Location of targets of archaeological interest

Although the focus has been mostly on shipwrecks, targets also include submerged structures, harbour and city installations, and scattered artifacts (canons, anchors, ritual vessels etc), among others.

-Applied interdisciplinary methodologies

Multibeam and side-scan sonar surveys, Sub-bottom profiling and seabed classification

For the **location of shipwrecks**, multibeam surveys performed in a large scale are primarily used. Side-scan sonar surveys remains a cost-effective solution for mapping seabed topography in low resolution, with no precise texture rendering, covering extended sea zones. It represents the best solution for the location of shipwrecks and the mapping of large sea-floor areas. Multibeam surveys are also used for the general documentation of big shipwrecks lying in great depths, where photogrammetric techniques are too costly to be applied (Barto Arnold 1981; Penrose et al. 2005; Papatheodorou et al. 2005, 2014; 2017; Gron et al. 2015; Yamafune et al. 2017; Zhu et al. 2019; Ferentinos et al. 2020).

A sub-bottom profiler acoustic survey provides supplementary data on seabed composition for contextualizing remote sensing results (Papatheodorou et al. 2005). Recent surveys have demonstrated the utility of sub-bottom profiles in distinguishing shipwreck-sized geological outcrops from potential shipwrecks (Sakellariou et al. 2007; Fakiris et al. 2016; Ferentinos et al. 2020). They also offer sections of the shipwrecks, if these are substantially covered by the sediments. Magnetometer surveys complement the aforementioned methods being efficient for the buried extension of a shipwreck (Mazotos, 4th c. BC, Cyprus- Demesticha et al. 2014) or the identification of different construction materials in the Roman harbour of Caesaria Maritima in Israel.

For the **paleoshoreline reconstruction**, a network of **sub-bottom profile lines vertical** to the shoreline is designed and performed. The results can reveal the presences of successive rocky palaeoshorelines or other features useful for the overall coastal reconstruction during the centuries (Papatheodorou et al. 2008, 2018; Geraga et al. 2015). These methods and techniques have been used effectively for the research of the prehistoric European continental shelf and elsewhere in the world, in order to reconstruct prehistoric landscapes and human distribution (Bailey et al. 2020; Missiaen et al. 2017; Bailey et al. 2007; Bailey 2009; Flemming et al. 2014). This research has been advanced in the framework of European projects, such as **SPLASH-COS** 2010-2013 (SUBMERGED PREHISTORIC ARCHAEOLOGY AND LANDSCAPES OF THE CONTINENTAL SHELF – COST – European Cooperation in Science and Technology), while innovative survey techniques have been addressed at **SASMAP** 2013-2016 (DEVELOPMENT OF TOOLS AND TECHNIQUES TO SURVEY, ASSESS, STABILISE, MONITOR AND PRESERVE UNDERWATER ARCHAEOLOGICAL SITES).

Finally, **airborne and underwater laser scanning systems** operating with green laser beams have been also used effectively in archaeological sites (Doneus et al. 2015). Bathymetric Lidar sensors can give information on bathymetry but also on topography. They can be used for the documentation of large archaeological zones offering detailed archaeological mapping and reconnaissance.

Recently, efforts have been done at combining methodologies, essentially to integrate underwater data captured by acoustic and optical systems, i.e. to combine acoustic data and photomosaics, as was attempted in a Roman Mediterranean wreck at 800m deep (Singh et al. 2000).

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Figure 1: Aigina Harbour-city Project. Mission 2019. Aerial and underwater 3D photogrammetry, Total Station measurements of the ancient naval city of the 5th c. BC. A dataset that is used experimentally in the NEANIAS project. @ Hellenic Ministry of Culture, EUA/ Aix-Marseille Université - CCI. Aerial Photogrammetry drone @L. Fadin, EFA 2019. Unpublished report 2019 (EUA - Hellenic Ministry of Culture)

2.1.2. Marine Environmental Sciences and Submarine Geohazards

Despite many years of effort, less than 20 per cent of the world ocean’s seafloor has been mapped. **Modern MultiBeam EchoSounders (MBES)** enable for high-resolution seabed mapping even in deep sea. Besides bathymetry (depth measurements), a seabed backscatter is retrievable which can be utilized for a remote guess in seabed classification. Accomplished by ground truth (geological and biological sampling) a bathymetric GIS analysis focusing on geomorphology, structural geology and tectonics enables a researcher to produce thematic maps. These are the basis of interpretations of marine habitats, sedimentary processes like erosion or deposition e.g. contourite deposits formed by deep water bottom currents, slope stability and pronounces submarine geohazard areas that could cause tsunami events, mass transport deposits, plate tectonic interpretations and many more.

The knowledge of seafloor topography is crucial for the understanding of the ocean and natural processes, especially for coastal and marine spatial planning and sustainable development. Marine

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geohazards pose unknown risk to the nearby communities and offshore infrastructures. The major geohazards include, but are not limited to, coastal erosion, submarine landslides, earthquakes and co-seismic displacement triggering tsunamis, underwater volcanism and hydrothermal fields, gas chimneys etc. One of first steps for the geohazard assessment is to “map” these hazards and then perform detailed morphological and quantitative analyses i.e. volume calculations, usage of sophisticated algorithms to identify seabed patterns and features like depressions, gullies morphological discontinuities and possible differences through time, etc. The integration of the aforementioned analyses with other kind of data such as side-scan mosaic, sediment cores and seismic data can lead to a holistic approach to risk assessment, habitat and geological mapping.

The usage of MBES revolutionized the marine surveys with respect to the quality, amount, precision of data and the ship time needed. Geohazard studies aim to identify the geological features underlying potential risk, and the objective of each study dictates the equipment used, the survey design and the acquisition parameters. In general, the usage of the MBES provides two kinds of data:

- a) the bathymetric data from which delivers depth information and
- b) the backscatter-intensity of the reflected signal that gives an insight of the sediment type.

Nonetheless, the processing of the data should follow a specific pipeline in order to secure the best quality of the end-products, which are the Digital Terrain Model (DTM) and the backscatter mosaic. Both are utilized for derivate or to be integrated with other datasets to quantify/model the risk.

While post-processing the data, there are many challenges to overcome, not only to meet the requirements of the International Hydrographic Organization (IHO) in case of the hydrographers use for nautical charts and navigation, but also to create a reliable end product for engineers and researchers who further analyse depending on each one’s needs. This approach is focused on the latter.

Firstly, we have to verify that the software can handle and parse correctly all the information needed from data acquired through different MBES and acquisition software, since almost each vendor has developed its own, mostly binary format. This is one of the main challenges to tackle because often we need to produce a final product derived from different datasets, thus different raw file formats, at least to produce a common bathymetric grid (DTM).

One of the parameters, during the acquisition, that introduces the most significant errors in the horizontal and vertical plane is the sound speed through the water column. When processing the data, it is mandatory to apply sound speed profiles obtained from different sensors. Besides that, a correction of the given attitude sensor offsets for e.g. roll, pitch, heave or heading might be as necessary as the correction for tide or draft.

In case of AUV/ROV recorded datasets even a correction of the georeferenced beams is commonly needed. This happens through manipulation or replacement of the navigation information. An accurate timestamp given to the data during acquisition (transmit and receive time) is a must-have to apply all the mentioned above. This is only granted by GPS or time-server synchronization.

During the editing of the data, it is important to have a variety of filters to choose since, for instance, when processing data acquired from a volcanic field where topographic changes are pronounced, a

slope filter would lead to undesired results. Depth filter might powerfully speed up editing while time and/or angular varying gain filters might help improving the backscatter results. Basic statistics like the standard deviation and data density for every grid cell given are essential to estimate a level of confidence.

Finally, since the DTM is needed for further geomorphological and quantitative analyses, an export to open and sustainable formats like GeoTIFF, ASCII, netCDF etc. is mandatory. One of the most widely used file formats is the Bathymetric Attributed Grid (BAG), that is designed to store and exchange bathymetric data combined with all the metadata. It has been stated that MB-System is currently not able to export BAG nor calculate/create TPU (Total Propagated Uncertainties) values. Nevertheless, both are important features for Hydrographers but not necessarily for marine research or underwater engineering.

2.1.3. Oil & Gas engineers, Renewable Energy Planners

Offshore developments, under no doubt, require high levels of reliability, flexibility, experience and project management. Most of the time, such projects require customized solutions with respect to the designing and planning phases, the pipe manufacturing and its accompanying infrastructures.

Oil and gas submarines pipelines as well as submarine transmission lines related to renewable energy require several surveys regarding the EU liabilities. Some of the studies required to be submitted are the following:

- System Screening & Optimization Study
- Overall System Hydraulics
- Onshore Route Feasibility
- Offshore Route Feasibility
- Consultation with Authorities, to identify constraints for landfalls, offshore and onshore pipeline
- Preliminary Environmental Impact Assessment Studies
- Preliminary Safety Study
- Cost and Schedule Estimating
- Compressor Stations and Pipelines design
- Reporting & Presentation of the Studies

In the abovementioned studies, all three proposed services developed and provided by NEANIAS can be used in order to maximize the designing, planning, development and licensing processes. Marine surveys have been carried out by developers in order to improve the accuracy of the pipeline route. The equipment required for those surveys, which were separated to offshore sector, nearshore sector and on shore sector as well as to submarine lines, are included in the following^[1]:

For the offshore sector:

- Multi-purpose offshore survey vessel for deployment of conventional survey equipment and AUV (Autonomous Underwater Vehicle),
- Deep water AUV with pipeline route survey payload,
- Surface and underwater positioning systems,
- Precision echo sounder,

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- Multi-beam echo sounder(s): shallow and deep-water depth rated,
- Sub-bottom profilers (shallow and medium penetration),
- 2DHR seismic system,
- Piston gravity corer,
- Cone penetrometer,
- Box corer,
- Vibrocorer.

For the nearshore sector:

- Survey launch,
- Survey positioning system,
- Self-elevating platform,
- Multi-beam echo sounder,
- Sub-bottom profilers (shallow and medium penetration),
- Seismic refraction spread,
- Vibrocorer,
- Borehole capability.

For the onshore sector (nearshore and landfall):

- Survey control,
- Topographic survey,
- Sub-surface profiling systems (resistivity and/or refraction),
- Geotechnical (borehole) drilling.

For the submarine pipelines (data required to proceed with the designing and route planning phase):

- Environmental baseline survey,
- Utility crossing survey,
- Possible data gathering in connection with archaeological sites,
- Environmental assessment and any other feature or activity that could potentially affect the proposed pipeline,
- Advanced geohazard investigations and related laboratory testing,
- Meteocean data acquisition,
- Hydrogeology.

With respect to the efforts and practices associated with the surveys, these should include topographic/bathymetric, hydrographic, high-resolution geophysical, seismic (2DHR) and geotechnical data. These data are considered crucial for the establishment of the existing topography and the seabed bathymetric surface (DTM), the determination of the sub-surface stratigraphy and shallow geology and the identification of potential hazards. In terms of sub-surface and shallow geology data, these are commonly processed through high-resolution geophysical datasets, correlated with geotechnical sampling and in-situ testing. Potential hazards referring to geological

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features and geotechnical phenomena, consist of various information regarding the installation and the operation of the pipeline through the projects life and thus are needed for the geohazards risk assessment of the project.

Datasets requirements of the AIGAIO Project related to the NEANIAS novel EOSC services

With the view to developing the deliverables of NEANIAS while finalizing the desktop study of the AIGAIO project, with total wind energy capacity of 582 MW on remote and uninhabited islets of the Aegean Sea, the Cyclades and the Dodecanese complex, EUNICE as an underwater end-user in the context of NEANIAS, aims to utilize all essential elements, available in Open-Source repositories and databases for the sufficient knowledge of the seafloor geomorphology and topography, which is necessary for the cable route survey and the reassurance of the cable route security as well as for the ports' design study. Since the AIGAIO Project refers to the installation of 138 wind turbines on scattered, remote, uninhabited and non-interconnected islands, major milestone of the project is the interconnection of the already licensed RES projects on these islands through the construction of a submarine DC transmission link. The main link will be the HVDC link connecting the island of Levitha, where the main power substation of the project shall be located, with the metropolitan area of Athens, and more specifically with the Ultra High Voltage Center (400kV) of Lavrion, which will be the exact connection point. The exploitation of accurate information and precise analysis for the seafloor and geomorphology of the Aegean Sea is crucial for the design, selection and installation of the submarine cabling and thus, for the planning of the total cost of the interconnections located in the greater area of the Aegean Sea.

Eunice, as an underwater end-user within the context of NEANIAS, aims to ultimately exploit all know-how offered by the Underwater Service Providers and available essential elements for the sufficient knowledge of the seafloor geomorphology and topography provided through the developed novel EOSC services, the former of which, are necessary for the cable route survey and the reassurance of the cable route security as well as for the ports' design study. Additionally, data resulting from the fieldwork regarding certain aspects during the implementation of the project can be further be used in order to test, enhance and improve the NEANIAS proposed EOSC services.

Marine geological surveys related data specification

The landing sites of the cables and the route of the total submarine cabling will be designed according to the sea – floor mosaicking and the geomorphology of the seafloor. A desktop study has already been developed, but further data regarding the seafloor mosaicking are important for the design of the submarine cabling route, which is in need of finalization and conclusively for the study to be appropriately updated. When choosing a landing site for the transmission cable, the following characteristics are taken into consideration:

- Rocky landing site with pockets of gravel.
- The landing site is partially sheltered from wave action, remaining vulnerable to waves from the west.
- The lines of the National seashore part of the beach and the consecutive beach corridor (shoreline and coastline) have been defined according to the law.

In cable route surveys, bathymetric contours and slope gradient, which are the primary terrain attributes, are extracted from DTMs, the latter of which constituting a basic requirement for the cable route designing. A more advanced seabed analysis is performed after the completion of geophysical data collection using single and multi-beam echo sounders (SBES & MBES), side scan sonars (SSS),

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sediment sub-bottom profilers (SBP), seabed geotechnical and sedimentological samplings. Moreover, a detailed seabed terrain analysis and bathymetric features may then be presented in geological and geomorphological maps.

Bathymetry constitutes the main source of information on the morphology of the seafloor, which is important for the final designing of the cable route. The required data interpretation starts with the classification of the bathymetric features into flat, sloping terrain, crests, depressions and breaks of slope. Bathymetric features like ridges, depressions and channels need also to be identified directly from the bathymetry.

At this point, it should be pointed out that all data can be used in order to create thematic maps (QGIS, AutoCAD) containing information on the sailing line (navigational channel), buoys, marinas, and lock and dam structures as well as underwater hazards such as pipelines and cables. These maps can then be used to redefine and therefore, optimize the route design of the submarine transmission cable. Data in raster and shapefile format are more appropriate as input files in QGIS through which can be later checked for locational and bathymetric accuracy.

MBES backscatter data regarding the seabed composition, are also useful for the designing process of the cabling route. Those data, can be utilized for the seabed mapping, indicating the variability of seabed composition including sediment types, seabed features (natural and manmade), rock outcrops, etc., all based on the variations of physical impedance of the acoustic signal during the inspection of the seabed. These data are significant for the survey of submarine cable systems in shallow water and burial areas. Moreover, the location of wrecks and archaeological is essential to be known and taken into consideration during, when defining the submarine cable route, so that not passing through those areas is ensured.

Moreover, the data sets generated by the MBES can be analyzed and imported in QGIS to generate a geospatial representation of the information that will be collected.

Multiple data types such as sidescan sonar or MBES backscatter imagery, bathymetric data, sub-bottom and magnetic intensity data can further assist the efforts of the underwater cable installation engineers. The seafloor mosaicking will be used as a base map in QGIS software where it serves to ground-truth and provide a visual representation of the true location of features. Furthermore, existing cable features will be revealed. These cables cannot be completely identified through the visualization as the cables are buried beneath the sediment in many instances. Nevertheless, in the locations where the cable itself is not visible in the generated imagery, the disruption of sediment associated with the cable routes reveals the approximate cable location. In linear surveys, as in the case of the submarine transmission cable, these data will be able to provide the exact location, detailed images and surrounding seabed to burial depths. Hence, the burial depths of the cable can be accurately defined through these data.

Furthermore, hazards such as tsunamis, fault zones and volcanoes need to be taken into consideration in the designing process of the submarine cable route. Obviously, all the above-mentioned data will be also processed through AutoCAD after the implementation of the required data manipulation and transformation. The main requirements of the underwater cable legislation and standards (ELOT) are outlined below.

Regarding the available planning tools, these include, but are not limited to, QGIS, Autocad and Google Earth.

Required data for the optimal cable and pipelines design

Furthermore, in the context of a preliminary approach concerning optimal cable and pipelines design, the following data are required:

- Location of existing and planned cables and repeaters
- Location of existing and planned pipelines
- Record of relevant cable failures' causes
- Maritime boundary delimitations
- Military exercise areas
- Dumping grounds
- Marine park boundaries
- Geoscience inputs (metocean, tectonics, volcanism)
- Bathymetric data
- Sonar imagery data
- Sub surface data
- Seabed surface features

Key uses of the data provided by the NEANIAS' project services, where designing the route of a transmission line takes place, are the following:

- Identify an area where the cable can be installed
- Develop a baseline of the environmental conditions
- Design a final cable route
- Specify the cable protection requirements
- Identify particular hazards along the cable route
- Identify the installation methods that can be used
- Predict performance of cable burial tools
- Contribute to modelling potential sediment transport at site
- Predict long-term changes to the seabed, such as moving sand waves, that might need to be monitored.

Moreover, information regarding qualitative early landing site evaluation and qualitative identification of some hazards is also necessary. Finally, in the phase of the selection of the appropriate submarine cable installation method and vessel in order to proceed with the cable laying operation, the basic requirements are the following:

- the water depth
- the distance between sea level and the overboard chute at the CLV (Cable Laying Vessel)
- the bottom tension at the TDP (touch down point)
- the cable's weight in water and the cable's weight in air

Furthermore, regarding the feasibility study, it has to be mentioned that it will be dominated by geophysical methods which characterize the seabed, the seabed mobility and the shallow geology that describe the promoted location for cable routing. In order to proceed with this feasibility study, data referring to bathymetry, side-scan sonar survey, echo sounder survey, acoustic sub-bottom profile and magnetometer survey were used. It has to be highlighted that, geotechnical methods are normally limited to drop cores and grab samples.

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In general, the cable routing survey normally includes environmental, geotechnical and geophysical data and testing such as, high resolution bathymetry, side-scan sonar, sub-bottom profiling, cone penetration testing, vibra-core and grab sampling. Also, through the development process of the pre-installation engineering of the cable/pipe, the project developer must provide the installer with data regarding specific conditions of the project, such as the seabed conditions and the depths in order to define the burial depths, the preferred approach and the specific tools and equipment in order to proceed with the laying of the cable. It is certain that, the amount and the quality of the seabed information, is crucial for the success of the cable installation. Moreover, these data will contribute to the risk analysis of the entire cable routing. MBES data are needed to proceed with the pre-lay surveys of the cable routing.

NEANIAS services can be utilized also in the phase of as-laid survey and the phase of as-built/verification survey. In the as-laid survey, some common practices to verify the cable's condition are, the acoustic inspection using towed sensor or a swath bathymetry system, acoustic inspection using 3D imaging sonar and inspection of the cable over the seabed. In as-built/verification survey phase, the cable has already been laid and buried. In this survey, the positioning and the burial depth of the cable consist the basic elements examined. In order to proceed with this survey, the methods that are usually applied are, the acoustic inspection of the sub-bottom profile, sub-bottom imaging and MBES surveys.

Finally, the risk management framework is a phase required to proceed with the development of a submarine cable/pipe. According to INTERNATIONAL STANDARD ISO/FDIS 31000 ISO, the risk assessment is the overall process of risk identification, risk analysis and risk evaluation. Within the cable burial risk assessment, all data related to hazards, geotechnical data, geophysical data, geological data and bathymetry, are needed.

2.1.4. Robotics & Computer Vision

With cameras being one of the cheapest and more commonly mounted sensors in underwater vehicles, the use of computer vision techniques for processing the large amounts of optical data has been used from the early beginnings of underwater robotics. The vehicles, either remotely operated (ROVs) or autonomous (AUVs), normally gather images during the course of the underwater mission. However, the field of view of a single image is quite limited. In fact, due to the rapid attenuation of light in the media, normally the images should be taken very close to the surveyed scene in order to have decent visibility. Therefore, in order to have a general view of the surveyed area after the mission, the collected images must be composed into an overall representation that allows extracting a global view of the area, which is a process called optical mapping. Depending on the type of output map required, we find photomosaicking techniques, which result in a 2D image of the area, or 3D mosaicking/reconstruction methods, whose result is a textured triangle mesh.

Under ideal conditions, both techniques can work with images alone to provide the desired map. However, maps extracted from images alone present some limitations. On the one hand, in case of using a monocular camera, the maps are affected by an unknown scale factor. That is, the map is not metric, and while it can be used to capture the shape and structure of the surveyed site, it cannot be used to make measurements on it. On the other hand, due to the lack of a global frame, the map is not geo-referenced, which makes it difficult to compare with other maps available of the area.

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Fortunately, robotic platforms are usually equipped with navigation sensors, providing hints on where the robot was at a given moment in time during the mission. This navigation information can be mixed in the optical mosaicking process in order to:

(1) Ease the mosaicking process: as it provides hints for which images should be matched together for composing the map.

(2) Improves the navigation of the vehicle: the motion computed from images is normally more accurate when close to the seafloor than the commonly used acoustic solutions for navigation (Doppler Velocity Log, Ultra Short Base Line, etc.). By mixing the image registration process with the navigation readings within a global alignment procedure (non-linear minimization of all measurements), the navigation itself is effectively improved.

(3) Provide metric and/or georeferenced maps: the metric scale of the navigation is used to infer the missing metric scale of the image-based measurements. If the navigation readings are also georeferenced, the resulting map will also be in that global frame.

The resulting 2D or 3D maps can then be used to plan new missions (path planning), but also as a base for further inference on the data, such as detecting and segmenting instances of objects or flora/fauna of interest present in the images. In this direction, the global map can be used to manually annotate the instances of the entities a given end-user may be interested in finding. This data can then be used to train a machine learning pipeline so that the marked entities can be automatically detected in maps from different missions.

2.1.5. Insurance

With respect to the insurance scheme of a wind park project, and in this case the AIGAIO Project that will be used as the main case-study in the framework of the NEANIAS project, the insurance covers all phases of wind farm construction and operation and it can be separated into two periods: the project insurance during the construction period and the project insurance during the operation period. It is worth noting that, there is no standard insurance policy for a wind farm meaning that especially for the Aegean project, which is a completely novel project, the insurance policy will be a tailored mixture of many different policies to meet the project's unique requirements.

The project insurance scheme during the construction period applies to the wind turbines' equipment being installed on site location, the employer's civil liability of the project owner and the General and Professional Liability. In more detail, regarding the wind turbines, the insurance has to do with the transit physical damage coverage, effective when the transportation of the components to the installation site initiates and the time delay exposure coverage, which insures against the lost power production revenues due to Transit Delay or Construction delays. The elements that are requested in order to proceed with that insurance program are: the supply contracts; delivery, approval and commissioning schedules; the location of loading and unloading of the project's components; the specific cost and type of wind turbines that will be installed and also the expected energy production of the specific wind park, along with the current selling price of energy. Liability insurance covers the responsibility of the project owner and the subcontractors working on the construction of the project. In order to proceed with this type of insurance the elements requested are the analytical schedule for construction of the entire project, information about subcontractors and subcontractors for each

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subject, contract amount of each contractor/subcontractor and the Health and Safety Plan. Finally, regarding the employer's civil liability, in order to proceed with the activation of it, the requested details refer to the notification of the number of employees of the project owner working on the construction of the project.

Secondly, the project insurance during the operation period applies to the security of property and mechanical damages of the wind turbines and the insurance of civil and employer liability. Regarding the security of property and mechanical damages of the wind turbines, the requested data is about the total machinery supply and maintenance contracts, the expected monthly power output per wind turbine, a brief description of the whole project and, in large projects such as the Aegean, the insurance company will also request that an independent expert reviews both the construction and the risk assessment study. It is worth noting that the cost of such a study would be extremely high, possibly reaching around € 400,000. Last but not least, as far as the insurance of civil and employer liability is concerned the details required appear to be the same as the ones required in the insurance of the construction period.

Regarding the insurance policy for the project's power transmission system, there are several requirements that need to be met. Necessary information needed to be provided in order to proceed with the insurance are the followings:

- Routing design (i.e., Design risk, natural risk, casualty exposure)
- Expected cover requirements
- Business plan
- Electrical Grid structure
- Power System Protection Design, i.e., Insulators and surge arresters (Raw material, manufacturing and workmanship risk)
- Conductors: Design, raw material, manufacturing and workmanship risk

As far as the insurance aspects are concerned, those can be classified in three sections and can be divided in intrinsic and external factors, as it is presented below:

SECTION 1 Material Damages: Intrinsic factors

- Knowledge of the System's designer VS location
- Exposure (location, access...)
- Method of cable laying
- Specifications of main equipment
- Project Management references

SECTION 2 TPL (Third party liability): Intrinsic factors

- Routing
- location and connection points of the grid

SECTION 3 DSU (Delay in Start Up): Intrinsic factors

- Routing/ Design
- Foundations
- Project scope
- Project buffer period
- Manufacturer QA

SECTION 1 Material Damages: External factors

- Grid structure
- Location (Natural exposure)
- Project scope (substations)

SECTION 2 TPL (Third party liability): External factors

- Grid structure
- Location (access)
- Project scope (substations)

SECTION 3 DSU (Delay in Start Up): External factors

- Grid structure
- Location (access)
- Manufacturers choice (location)

2.2. Underwater Datasets and Products

Retrieving underwater environmental information based on remote sensing technologies requires either hydroacoustic, photogrammetric or laser devices, no matter which kind of investigation is undertaken. Nevertheless, Underwater Archaeologists, Geologists, Biologists or Engineers etc., the overall aim would be the creation of diverse thematic maps, 3D models and figures out of the basic products of the underwater services, like bathymetric or multi-frequency/multispectral maps, backscatter or ortho-rectified or 3D photo-mosaics.

2.2.1. Data and Products for Archaeologists

The essential parameters for the development of the NEANIAS services for the underwater archaeological community are the following:

A. Photomosaicking: Scale, precision, accuracy

A1. Scale:

The scale of archaeological recording is completely different from the one taken into account in geological or biological prospections. Shipwrecks and structures (walls, architecture, monuments, artefacts) need to be mapped at specific mapping scales, in order to be able for archaeologists to draw precise archaeological plans that can be useful as serious archaeological documentation. Otherwise, the photogrammetric model is useful as an illustrative product (a good representation respecting form and texture), but cannot be considered or used as scientific documentation.

A2. Precision

Archaeological documentation requires higher precision, in order to allow for the structures and objects to be studied in detail. Therefore, according to the site and special conditions taken into account (turbidity of the water, etc.), we can usually accept an error of millimeters for the documentation of a wreck (otherwise the original dimensions of the internal parts of the ship are distorted in the final plan), or archaeological structures with architectural details. This precision can be compromised to up to a few centimeters, if we are studying a submerged site or an anchorage on a larger scale. In any case, the precision required for the production of scientific documentation is generally much higher than the one required for a geological survey.

A3. Accuracy

Accuracy is essential. The structures documented (and less the shipwrecks lying in deep water) need to be accurately located in the sea-floor or the ocean. Otherwise, in a wider scale, the topographical location of the underwater archaeological features loses its real topographical relationship (i.e. during the study of a submerged city, of a harbour complex, etc). Of course, accuracy is proportional to the conditions of the photogrammetric recording (to the resolution and the scale of the photographs) and other parameters (Drap 2012).

B. Bathymetry - Seabed classification

When considering the novel NEANIAS EOSC services, the parameters required from the underwater archaeological community are the following:

When large databases of geological data are processed, algorithms and other parameters may be developed for the **location of possible targets of UCH and locations of interest**, such as shipwrecks, submerged sites, built structures, sunken artifacts, commercial routes, etc. This can be achieved by studying specific requirements that will help towards facilitating the location of certain geometries, shapes and sizes, as well as different textures and materials (ceramic amphorae, metal shipwrecks of the World Wars I and II, canons, built structures of submerged cities).

Moreover, we need very detailed processing of results from databases produced by sensors designed already for high-resolution surveys (resolution and accuracy in the order of millimeter).

Furthermore, it has to be taken into account that these targets are located as anthropogenic intrusions in natural marine environments and biological habitats (such as, sandy or silty sea-floor, *poseidonia* valleys, rocky substratum, etc.). Therefore, benthic terrain models (BTM) could be studied within an archaeological scope and be able to identify geological and anthropogenic targets of UCH. Following site formation processes of ancient shipwrecks and submerged settlements, these are always studied with their natural environment: the study can be more comprehensive and interdisciplinary, with mutual benefits for all underwater scientific communities.

Thus, databases from the oil and gas industries or renewable energy companies, that are performed in large-scale areas of the sea-floor may offer invaluable information on UCH from the quality software treatment of the results.

C. Geo-referencing system

All surveys are performed with respect to a global reference system, that is fundamental to archaeological documentation. However, geo-referencing is not always done in the same way during different marine surveys or photogrammetric recording, while not all mobile systems can use satellite-positioning systems. Other deep-water surveys of shipwrecks or other targets are performed in a local reference system and then geo-referenced through reference points of known coordinates (Menna et al. 2018). Therefore, it is important to consider all these parameters when dealing with the export of different information, when processing different databases in the NEANIAS services.

D. Data-storage and accessibility now and in the future

From all interdisciplinary archaeological and geological prospections, the resulting models, together with the photogrammetric georeferenced data and all the survey data, are stored in a repository database for further use and interrogation. However, these bases are not stored in an open-access

database that they are not accessible to the research community. We hope that the way the services of NEANIAS will be implemented, will promote accessibility and interconnectivity between the interdisciplinary communities.

Case studies from underwater archaeology

- Submerged cities

An exemplary case of a submerged city documented and mapped with a combination of methodological tools and underwater prospection techniques is the Roman city of Baiae in Naples, sunken after the eruption of the Vesuvius and the subsequent tectonic activity during the Roman period (Bruno et al. 2015). Laser scanner reliefs of selected archaeological structures in the submerged Baiae (Petriaggi- Ayala 2015), as well as the multi-beam documentation of the submerged structures in the Pozzuoli harbour show the level of accuracy obtained for the documentation of submerged UCH (Passaro et al. 2013).

Figure 2: Multi-resolution morpho-bathymetric survey of submerged archaeological remains at Pozzuoli (Naples, Italy). Passaro et al. 2013.

Other successful initiatives include the 3D documentation of the prehistoric site of Pavlopetri in Greece, an extended site lying in shallow water (Henderson et al. 2013; Mahon et al. 2011).

Two datasets to be used in the framework of the NEANIAS project will be provided by the interdisciplinary survey, mainly *Aigina Harbour-city Project*, a submerged city in the island of Aigina, and *Palaia Phokaia* in Attica. Both submerged cities are lying at very shallow waters from 0.00 to -5m depth. They are surveyed and documented by interdisciplinary teams with a combination of methods, mainly Total Station, 3D underwater and aerial photogrammetry and marine geosciences

prospections. In both cases, accuracy and precision are key parameters to be achieved in the post-processing of the data; otherwise, a number of architectural details will be lost.

Figure 3: Aigina Harbour-city Project 2019-2023. Greece. 3D underwater photogrammetric recording used systematically to document and monitor the progress of the archaeological excavation. Above a combination of the photogrammetric documentation and Total Station recording. @Ministry of Culture, EUA / Aix-Marseille Université – CCJ – MoMArch / EFA, photos: L.Roux (CNRS-CCJ), photogrammetry : J. Anbar (AMU, MoMArch – NKUA) 2020.

Figure 4: Palaia Phokaia Survey 2019. Submerged ancient city in Attica, Greece. Unpublished report 2019. Hellenic Ministry of Culture-EUA, Aix-Marseille University. @K. Baika CCJ-CNRS-AMU

- Location and recording of Shipwrecks

One of the first photogrammetric recording *in situ* of a shipwreck was implemented on an underwater archaeological excavation of the Grand Ribaud F, a deep Etruscan shipwreck discovered in 1999 in Hyères, France. The wreck is of high archaeological interest for both its cargo and its state

of conservation. Found at 90 m depth, it dates to the 6th c. BC and it contains nearly 1,500 amphorae. In this case, the study went further on. The objective was not only to measure *in situ* the archaeological artifacts, but also to obtain a theoretical model from the partially measured object, the amphora, through measured geometry and geometrical computation (Drap et al. 2001; Drap 2012). This initiative was also carried on the Phoenician Xlendi wreck in Malta (Drap et al. 2015). In both cases, this innovative research depended on a high-accuracy underwater 3D photogrammetric model, as produced by the available software.

- Location by acoustic sensors and photogrammetric recording of a deep wreck

Another case-study is the unique Phoenician shipwreck of Xlendi, at Gozo island off Malta, discovered in a depth of 110m and now under excavation. The wreck was located during a side-scan sonar survey, and the potential sections and form of the ship were studied by the sub-bottom profiler survey (Gabin 2014, 2015, Gabin et al. 2018), demonstrating the potential of this kind of marine geological prospections for underwater archaeological research, as well as their added value if the results offer accuracy and precision.

Figure 5: Xlendi wreck, Malta, phoenician wreck 110m deep. Side-scan sonar survey and archaeological target (sonar image in 500kHz) (Gabin et al. 2018, figs. 2 and 3).

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Figure 6: Xlendi wreck Malta, Side-scan sonar and subbottom profiler survey showing sections of the shipwreck (Gabin et al. 2018, fig. 6)

Figure 7: Xlendi wreck, Malta. High-resolution orthophoto from the photogrammetric documentation 2014 (Gabin et al. 2018, fig. 10)

- 3D recording of a wreck in a depth of 40m

Another example is the photogrammetric recording of the pre-excitation phase of the amphora wreck of Mazotos in Cyprus lying in 40m depth and carrying Chian amphoras of the 4th c. BC. (Demesticha et al. 2014).

Other recent relevant case-studies have been published in McCarthy- Benjamin- Winton- Duivenvoorde (eds) (2018) collective volume.

2.2.2. Data and Products for Marine Environmental Scientists

Marine environmental science in general is dealing with a broad number of vendor formats from hydroacoustic devices to different underwater photo- and video-cameras. Their products are digital terrain models in various formats, backscatter and multispectral and photo-mosaics in formats like GeoTiff and at least after analysis, thematic maps produced with GIS in vector formats. Some examples with a different focus are shown below.

Investigations to tsunamis caused by submarine slope failures along western Great Bahama Bank led to a modelling based on bathymetric information. It revealed the potential risk for the eastern coast of Florida being hit by a tsunami (Schnyder et al (2016)).

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Figure 8: Figure (a) Slope failures along western Great Bahama Bank. b) Margin collapse and the associated mass wasting products on the southwest corner of GBB

In Figure 8: (a) Slope failures along western Great Bahama Bank. The scar visible on the lower slope and the associated mass transport complex in the basin. The smaller landslide was simulated using the extent of the middle part of the failure scar. The incipient failure scar (IFS), transect A-A' is also visible in the sub-bottom profile. (b) Margin collapse and the associated mass wasting products on the southwest corner of GBB. (The 3D bathymetry was produced using QPS Fledermaus v.7 <http://www.qps.nl/display/fledermaus/>. The sub-bottom profile was produced using Reflex v.6 (<http://www.sandmeier-geo.de/reflexw.html>).

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Figure 9: Tsunami wave propagation paths caused by (a) a submarine landslide (9 km width and $ut= 20 \text{ ms}^{-1}$) and (b) a margin collapse of southwestern GBB (12 km width and $ut= 20 \text{ ms}^{-1}$). (Map was created in MATLAB r2014a using GEBCO grids, <http://www.gebco.net>)

The Aegean volcanic arc has been investigated along its offshore areas and several submarine volcanic outcrops have been discovered in the last 30 years of research. The basic data including swath bathymetric maps, air-gun profiles, underwater photos and samples analysis have been presented along the four main volcanic groups of the arc: (i) Paphsanias submarine volcano in the Methana group, (ii) three volcanic domes to the east of Antimilos volcano and hydrothermal activity in southeast Milos in the Milos group, (iii) three volcanic domes east of Christiana and a chain of about twenty volcanic domes and craters in the Kolumbo chain northeast of Santorini in the Santorini group and (iv) several volcanic domes and a volcanic caldera together with very deep slopes of several volcanic islands in the Nisyros group (Nomikou et al (2013). Most of the swath data from the Aegean Sea will be used in NEANIAS project.

Figure 10: Synthetic onshore and offshore topographic map of the South Aegean Sea showing the four volcanic Groups (Nomikou et al., 2013). Inset map: The Geodynamic setting of the Hellenic Orogenic Arc

Mud extrusion and ring-fault gas seepage – upward branching fluid discharge at a deep-sea mud volcano (Loher et al. 2018).

Mud volcanoes (MVs) are geological structures created by the extrusion of sediments, water, and volatiles (predominantly methane) from deeply-rooted plumbing systems that remain poorly understood. Two seepage domains are recognized at the Venere MV, the currently only active site in the Calabrian Arc: mud breccia extrusion from a summit, and hydrocarbon venting from peripheral sites, hosting chemosynthetic ecosystems and authigenic carbonates indicative of long-term seepage. The AUV bathymetry shown below is part of the NEANIAS test data.

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Figure 11: AUV-derived bathymetry (1.6 m grid) of Venere mud volcano (MV) and sampling locations

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Figure 11 depicts AUV-derived bathymetry (1.6 m grid) of Venere mud volcano (MV) and sampling locations. A fresh mud flow (outlined in white) originating from the W summit extends down to the caldera floor. (a) Perspective view of Venere MV (generated in QPS Fledermaus 7.3.2b; www.qps.nl). Note twin cones labeled as E + W summit, each up to 100 m high and ring faults defining a caldera up to 3 km across. Water column gas flares (red to yellow colors; extracted from hydroacoustic data) up to 260 m in height were observed at five sites, along the peripheral ring faults (Sites 1, 2, 4, 5) and near the W summit (Site 3); (b) Map-view of Venere MV (see Fig. 1 for extent) with inset of the extrusion site of the fresh mudflow at the W summit (generated in ESRI ArcMap10.3.1; www.esri.com). Red stars mark the flare origins and white circles indicate sampling locations with white numbers referring to the last two Geo B-identifiers (see Table 1 and supplementary Tables S1 and S2 for full details of all stations). See supplementary Figs S2 and S3 for bathymetry without annotations and an alternative perspective view of a) showing the heights of ring faults.

Figure 12: Seafloor photographs

Figure 12 seafloor photographs: (a) ~10 m long transect across fresh (right) vs. older (left) mud breccia flows draped by hemipelagic sediments near the western summit (see inset of Fig. 2b for location); (b) western summit of Venere MV showing elevated extrusive center at the origin of the most recent mudflow (see inset of Fig. 2b for location); (c) authigenic carbonate crusts, cold-seep communities and sampling of gas bubbles at a peripheral seep (Site 5); (d) tubeworm colony rooting in a fracture of authigenic carbonate crust at a peripheral seep (Site 1); (e) cold-seep community and thick authigenic carbonate pavement at a peripheral seep (Site 1).

Coral Patch seamount (NE Atlantic) – a sedimentological and megafaunal reconnaissance based on video and hydroacoustic surveys (Wienberg et al (2013)).

In recent years seamounts have gained increasing interest mainly because of their possible important role as local biodiversity hotspots. For the first time a detailed hydroacoustic mapping (MBES) in conjunction with video surveys (ROV, camera sled) were performed on the Coral Patch seamount to describe the sedimentological and biological characteristics of this subelliptical ENE-WSW elongated seamount. Video observations were restricted to the southwestern summit area of Coral Patch seamount (water depth: 560–760 m). Based on these observations and ground truth an extended hydroacoustic seabed mapping was realized utilizing the benthic terrain modeler (BTM), a GIS habitat mapping tool.

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Figure 13: Hydroacoustic seabed classification maps (A: 2D-plots, B: 3D-plots) of Coral Patch seamount.

Figure 13 hydroacoustic seabed classification maps (A: 2D-plots, B: 3D-plots) of Coral Patch seamount. (1) Fine-scale and (2) broad-scale zonal classification maps both showing the distribution of geoform components (GC) comprising e.g., flat plains, slopes, boulders and local ridges (see Table 4 for detailed description). (3) Textural classification map showing the distribution of substrate components (SC; see Table 2 for detailed description). (4) "Side-scan" mosaic grid. Inserted boxes on (A) indicate video-surveyed area at the southwestern top of Coral Patch seamount, white dots show position of Van

Veen grab sampling, both used as ground-truthing data for textural seabed classification. The location of the training and test sites are denoted in (A) (3) and (4).

Figure 14: Flowchart of hydroacoustic seabed classification methods applied for Coral Patch seamount.

Figure 14 flowchart of hydroacoustic seabed classification methods applied for Coral Patch seamount. The dataset used for the flowchart displays a small area at the southwestern summit. The final

products (last image row) represent (a) topographical characteristics based on the bathymetry and derived products (BPI: Bathymetric Position Index), and (b) textural classes based on the "side-scan" mosaic and hillshade/slope.

2.2.3. Data and Products for Oil & Gas engineers

The following subsection provides information on projects with submarine transmission lines and the studies required in order to proceed with the finalization of the cabling route. Those projects consist case studies regarding subsea power transmission, submarine transition cable connecting RES projects to the mainland grid, gas and oil pipelines. Most of them are included by EU in PCI (Project of Common Interest).

A project worth highlighting as a reference point with respect to the engineering studies required is the **TANAP SCADA** System and Crossings under Dardanelle Strait and Evros River. It is actually a gas pipeline from the EU to Turkmenistan via Turkey, Georgia, Azerbaijan and the Caspian, currently known as the combination of the "Trans Anatolia Natural Gas Pipeline" (TANAP), the "Expansion of the South-Caucasus Pipeline" (SCP-(F) X) and the "Trans-Caspian Gas Pipeline" (TCP)". The connection between the Transatlantic Gas Pipeline (TAP) and the Anatolian Natural Gas Pipeline (TANAP) has been successfully completed in 2018 with the final "golden soldering" connecting the two conductors. For the design of the project, on Greek soil, geotechnical surveys and studies were compulsory for the construction of the TAP gas pipeline. In the above-mentioned project, the geotechnical survey included 99 rotaries, sample drillings and 80 Auger drillings, with a total depth of 1810m. In addition to this, it required performing on-site testing of SPT and MAAG as well as performed laboratory tests of soil engineering and rock engineering.

*Figure 15: TANAP SCADA System and Crossings under Dardanelle Strait and Evros River
(Source: https://ec.europa.eu/inea/sites/inea/files/7.1.1-0014-tr-s-m-15_action_fiche_final_0.pdf)*

The dredging at TANAP project has been completed. There is no seasonal constraint for marine construction because there is no breeding area in the sea crossing for marine fauna species. The cumulative impact assessment was performed considering some of the following data:

1. Physical environment:
 - Meteorology and climatology
 - Air Quality
 - Noise and Vibration
 - Hydrogeology and groundwater quality
 - Geology and Geomorphology
 - Seismology
 - Soil
 - Visual aesthetics
 - Hydrology and surface water quality
 - Bottom morphology
 - Physical oceanography
 - Sea water
 - Marine Sediments
2. Biological environment:
 - Protected areas
 - Terrestrial Flora
 - Terrestrial Fauna
 - Birds
 - Amphibians
 - Reptiles

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- Mammals
 - Invertebrates
3. Marine habitats and ecosystems
 4. Marine biodiversity
 5. Marine protected areas
 6. Social environment
 - Cultural heritage and archaeology
 - Ecosystem services

To continue with, **EuroAsia** Interconnector is another great example of application of data in order to proceed with the marine survey of the cabling route. The EuroAsia Interconnector consists of a 500 kV DC underwater electric cable with its associated equipment for interconnecting the Cypriot, Israeli and Greek transmission networks. The first phase of the interconnector is designed to have a capacity of 1,000 MW and a total length of around 1,518 km. It needs to be mentioned that this project is also a PCI. The project has already conducted the required studies and is entering the construction phase. An external marine survey was carried out in order to determine the preferred route for the cable. Also, a bathymetric study was carried out in order to accurately determine the route of the interconnector cable along the seabed. This survey aimed to establish and evaluate the existing seabed topography and morphology and moreover, to identify potential geological features. This survey consisted of a bathymetric investigation along the proposed route and a bathymetric investigation of the most critical areas from a bathy-morphological point of view. Further on, specific surveys were conducted such as burial assessment, so as to perform soil sampling by gravity and vibro corers and cone penetrometer test (CPT) at discrete intervals and locations determined by the geophysical results of Sub bottom profiler (SBP). Given the length for the whole survey, the extended deep-water areas, the high required resolution, ROV's and possibly AUV's were needed to be employed to increase the resolution of swath bathymetry (MBES), Side scan Sonar (SSS) and SBP and on-board data processing and charting were also performed for the route design process.

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Figure 16: EuroAsia Interconnector (Source: www.euroasia-interconnector.com)

Additionally, one more project of equal importance and worth to considerate within the framework of this current analysis, is the **Eastern Mediterranean pipeline (EastMed pipeline)**, which is a pipeline from offshore Cyprus to Greece mainland via Crete. The length of this gas pipeline is approximately 1,900km out of which, 1,300km of offshore and 600km of onshore pipeline sections. The EastMed pipeline project received approvals from the Cypriot, Greek, and Italian Governments in 2015 and has been added in the second PCI list and considered in the Southern Gas Corridor projects. IGI Poseidon signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with Israel Natural Gas Lines (INGL) in November 2019, followed by another MoU with TMNG, a subsidiary of Israeli oil and gas engineering company Tahal Group in December 2019. The European government has added the project in the last Ten Years Development Plan (TYNDP) of the European Network Transportation System Operators of Gas (ENTSO-G), which is aimed at creating a safe transmission network capable of meeting the current and future energy needs of Europe. The project includes a 200km offshore pipeline section with a diameter of 24in that will start from the Leviathan gas field of Israel and end at Cyprus connecting the Aphrodite gas field. A 100MW compressor station will be constructed at Cyprus. A 700km offshore pipeline section with a diameter of 26in will connect the pipeline further from Cyprus to Crete Island, where a 120MW compressor station will be installed.

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Figure 17: Offshore Seismic 2D Surveys in Lebanon – Oil & Gas Journal (Dunnahoe, 2017)

Figure 18: Offshore Seismic 3D Surveys in Lebanon – Oil & Gas Journal (Dunnahoe, 2017)

Eastern Mediterranean Natural Gas Pipeline, is part of PCI, therefore, pre-FEED studies were completed, in order to proceed with the project. In this context, a Technical Feasibility Studies' package, a Reconnaissance Marine Survey (RMS), as well as Economic, Financial and Competitiveness Studies were performed. The Technical Feasibility helped determining the best route together with the optimal pipeline configuration and the key technical risks, proving the technical viability and providing CAPEX and OPEX estimation. The project feasibility has been confirmed, clarifying that its configuration is well within the state of art of the available technology and proving the existence of pipelay vessels able to lay deep water pipelines. Moreover, a preliminary environmental impact assessment was successfully conducted. The RMS aimed to acquire bathymetric, geophysical and geotechnical data, contributing fundamentally to the overall assessment of the feasibility of the engineering and the installation of the marine pipeline sections. The outcomes of the RMS were integrated into the Feasibility Design that identified no showstoppers along the route and confirmed the CAPEX, estimated to be around 5.2 billion EUR for a 10 Bcm/y capacity. (https://ec.europa.eu/inea/sites/inea/files/cefpub/summary_7.3.1-0025-elcy-s-m-15_final.pdf).

Figure 19: The Eastern Mediterranean Pipeline (EastMed) (Source: <https://www.depa.gr/>)

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Furthermore, another significant example is the **Poseidon Pipeline**, which is a multi-source natural gas interconnector stretching from the Turkish-Greek border to Italy. The Poseidon Pipeline will extend for approximately 760 km on Greek territory (the onshore section) from the Turkish-Greek border in Kipi to the landfall in Florovouni and for approximately 216 km crossing the Ionian Sea up to the landfall in Italy and the receiving terminal in Otranto (the offshore section), where it will be connected to the Italian national gas transport system.^[1] The Poseidon project aims to transport gas between Greece and Italy at an initial volume of 14 bcm/y (first phase) and up to 20 bcm/y on a second phase. The project includes the following phases^[2]:

- Compression station in Thesprotia (120 MW)
- Onshore pipeline between the compression station and the Greek landfall
- New offshore pipeline of approximately 216 km with a capacity of up to 329.4 GWh/day between the Greek and Italian landfalls
- Onshore pipeline between the Italian landfall and the metering station in Otranto.

As far as the marine studies are concerned, those involve offshore and nearshore hydrographic, geophysical and geotechnical surveys. Those studies are linked with the EastMed study regarding the data required and the processing.

Regarding submarine interconnections, “**Project 293 – Southern Aegean Interconnector (SAI)**” can be highlighted due to the fact that this project refers to the construction of a submarine DC transmission link to connect the licensed RES plants at the South Aegean Sea to mainland Greece and the islands of Crete, Kos and the Dodecanese. It should be mentioned that it consists of a project considered in the reference grid. The interconnection of the AEGEAN Project has been included in the ten-year development plan of ENTSO-E as “Project 293 – Southern Aegean Interconnector (SAI)”. ENTSO-E is the European Network of Transmission System Operators, representing 42 electricity transmission system operators (TSOs) from 35 countries across Europe. ENTSO-E was established by European TSOs with a mandate by the EU’s Third Legislative Package for the Internal Energy Market in 2009, which aims at further liberalizing the gas and electricity markets in the EU.

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Figure 20: Project 293 – Southern Aegean Interconnector (SAI): location and submarine interconnection system. (Source: <https://tyndp.entsoe.eu/tyndp2018/projects/projects/293>, <http://igi-poseidon.com/en/poseidon>)

Besides all, **AIGAIO** refers to submarine interconnection for renewable energy projects, as it relates to the Aegean project. This new transmission line is currently under EIA licensing process and will link the Aegean project to the mainland Greece and Crete. It will also allow the connection of non-interconnected Dodecanese island complex, the islands of Kos, Leros, Nisyros, Kalymnos and Tilos to the main grid. In this case among others, the development process of the project, requires studies as the abovementioned. Therefore, all three of the developed NEANIAS services are critical for the optimal development and designing of the project.

Figure 21: AIGAIO project's location and submarine interconnection system (source: www.eunice-group.com)

Last but not least, a further project that can be helpful as a case study, is the **Celtic Interconnector**. The Celtic Interconnector is a proposed electrical link, which if built will enable the movement of power between Ireland and France (<http://www.eirgridgroup.com/>). A series of joint studies into the

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feasibility of the interconnector have been carried out with the French TSO Réseau de Transport d'Électricité (RTE) since 2011. In 2014, a marine geophysical survey was undertaken, in which following completion of each geophysical survey, locations for geotechnical sampling were identified and an assessment was made as to the likelihood of encountering Unexploded Ordnances (UXO) during sampling based on Side Scan Sonar (SSS) and magnetometer data. Furthermore, in 2015, a geotechnical and benthic survey campaign was performed. During those surveys data referring to surficial seabed were collected. Additionally, a marine archaeological survey was conducted and geophysical and geotechnical survey data were collected over the proposed route corridors. This survey aimed to identify known and potential sites and features of archaeological interest in the cable survey corridor that might be impacted by the project. Such sites are considered critical for the cabling design because, due to their impact on the project, which dictates a subsequent limitation through the adoption of the appropriate mitigation measures.

Figure 22:Celtic Interconnector Marine Route (Source: <http://www.eirgridgroup.com/>)

2.3. Underwater Software and Services

This section reports on the state of the art of the current software and tools (in TRL6) in use within the Underwater Research community.

2.3.1. Underwater archaeology community

Most underwater archaeologists and research teams are using **Agisoft Photoscan/Metashape Professional edition® software** for the processing of the photogrammetric models. It is user-friendly, continuously updated and is offering an easy access to the students of archaeology and young researchers. Archaeological projects are also low-budget and they are constrained to optimize results by collaboration with geoscientists, but also by using open access software.

In any case, Agisoft software is frequently used in order to produce orthogonal projections, sections and plans as supporting visual documentation in the framework of maritime research. However, many other different software suites are used for the pre- and post- processing of images and produced plans. For example, the underwater image pre-processing can be addressed from two different points of view: image restoration techniques or image enhancement methods, which do not require a priori knowledge of the environment (corrections such as non-uniform illumination, low contrast and muted colors) (Drap 2012b).

Thus, usual software includes **Abode Bridge®**, **Adobe Light-room®** and **Photoshop CS5®** to edit the color balance, the contrast, and the brightness properties of the photos. In a next step, generated 3D models of artefacts and structures and orthophotos extracted as 1:1 scaled top view photomosaics are used as the basis for drawing and tracing 2D and 3D site plans in other software, such **AutoCAD®** or **ArcGIS®** or **QGIS®** software, etc.

Therefore, one of the requirements from the underwater archaeology community would be to **produce a software** that could incorporate some of the above actions in order to reduce time and energy from the use of too many software tools for the pre- and post-processing operations.

2.3.2. Geologists, Oil & Gas engineers, Computer vision/machine learning engineers

Most scientists and in general R&D groups who are interested in underwater seabed classification of seafloor cover classes are using most of the times commercial software that is usually developed for land and land cover applications. These for example may include the commercial ENVIS or ERDAS Imagine software. The reason is that the aforementioned software is in most cases user-friendly and comes with a number of additional tools especially for supervised classification procedures and manual collection of training data/polygons. There are also a number of decent open-source software and plugins, executing classification pipelines like the semi-automatic Classification Plugin of QGIS. It should be mentioned that currently, to the best of our knowledge, there does not exist any software developed and tailored for seabed classification based on multispectral multibeam. In particular, most seabed classification tasks are performed from R&D groups implementing custom solutions per task or dataset. An example was the recent R2Sonic Multispectral Challenge on which many researchers from different scientific domains tried to discriminate the geomorphological features of the seabed by using multispectral multibeam data and in order to do so they proposed different supervised classification procedures based on e.g. Gaussian Models or Support Vector Machines with linear kernels (Gaida et al. (2017), Brown et al. (2017), Buscombe & Grams (2018), Snellen et al. (2018)).

2.3.3. Oil & Gas engineers, Renewable Energy Planners

Planners regarding submarine transmission and pipelines are using computer-aided engineering software such as AutoCAD and QGIS for the processing of georeferenced data. AutoCAD software provides the user with plenty menu options that are useful in order to proceed with the planning phase. QGIS platform is really useful during the designing process as it allows the connection of many items and synchronized edit process of them. Using the standard QGIS interface, the user shall establish a set of demands on address points and finally provide the parameters necessary for further steps of the algorithm.

A basic condition for the proper use of the software is the quality of the data in terms of validity and accuracy of approach to their geographical location. During the abovementioned process, it is crucial that all the data are referenced in a suitable coordinate system with great precision.

In general, many other specific software may be used for the transmission design. One of those is the Electra software, which is a powerful power line CAD design software that combines design and documentation production workflows for electrical distribution design. It provides sophisticated design and analyzing tools to optimize transmission network designs in plan and profile. Moreover, the integrated use of PIs-Cadd (structure spotting) and Tower (structural analysis) software consists also a common practice. Furthermore, RSTAB (Structural Frame & Truss Analysis Software) software that is used to process data regarding the laying of the submarine cable at an intermediate water depth. A non-linear static analysis is initially conducted to build up the catenary configuration.

In general, the basic input parameters required in order to proceed with the designing of the cable route are the following:

- The water depth
- Distance from the sea level of the overboard chute at the CLV
- Geometry of the overboard chute onboard the CLV
- Bottom tension at the TDP
- Cable weight in water
- Cable weight in air
- Non-linear diagrams (reaction force N/deflection mm) for the cable–soil interaction in two directions (X, Y)
- Composite cable flexural stiffness
- Composite cable axial stiffness

State of the art of the current software and tools

U1 - Bathymetry Mapping from Acoustic Data

MB-System (Caress & Chayes, 2017) is running in-house at UBREMEN, Teledyne in Denmark (Neanias U1 service responsible) is working closely with Teledyne in Bremen for bathymetric specialisms hence they have specialists in house using and working with MB-Systems, and worldwide in many other institutes and universities as a bathymetry and backscatter post-processing tool for MBES datasets. It is on a technology readiness level (TRL) 6, has been validated using different datasets from various vendors, and is under constant maintenance through the open-source community. Furthermore, the

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package is capable to realize navigation correction for AUV/ROV recorded bathymetry. This is crucial not just for bathymetry but for other acquired datasets like CTD/Photos/Videos a.s.o.

Underwater-recorded bathymetry lacks of accuracy since GNSS/RTK (Global Navigation Satellite Service/Real Time Kinematics) information cannot be used directly. A number of devices is necessary to accurately steer and position underwater devices like AUV/ROV (Autonomous and Remotely working Vehicles). Next to GNSS & RTK, which can only be used directly on the sea surface, USBL/LBL and DVL (Ultra Short & Long Base Line under water positioning and Doppler Velocity Log) and even the revolutions per minute of the vehicle's propellers are taken into account when solving the algorithms for positioning by utilizing Kalman filters during acquisition.

Still, the uncertainties are large unless the devices are operating very close to the seafloor and are capable to use photo/video information also for navigation decision making processes. This is rather seldom the case. Nevertheless, due to its numerous software dependencies, MB-System currently requires a deeper knowledge in the operating systems (Unix/Linux) and in the command line-based installation and execution of the different packages.

Utilizing MB-System for bathymetric and backscatter post processing is a very sustainable solution but as a matter of consequence when using command line, it lacks of certain workflows and logging of what have been applied to the data. Therefore, the user is obliged to document manually which commands he/she executed. A disadvantage with respect to metadata for quality standards or confidence levels.

U2 - Seafloor Mosaicing from Optical Data

The software for implementing U2 is currently running at in-house servers of CORONIS. The components required for this endeavor have been developed up to levels 5 (diagnostics task) and levels 6 (for the tasks of pre-processing and corrections, 2D mapping, 3D mapping). The final target for the NEANIAS project is to have it at TRL 8 at the end of the project.

Nevertheless, the current software requires a deeper knowledge on the different parameters needed to finally process the 2D photo-mosaic or the 3D representation (DTM). The challenge of the development behind this service is to make it robust to a wide range of input imaging conditions, which are representative of the intended science and commercial applications of the target user group. Making easy its use by non-experts.

U3 - Seabed Classification from Multispectral, Multibeam Data

U3 service focuses on the efficient exploitation of recent cutting-edge multibeam echosounders which go beyond the standard ones that collect backscatter at a single predefined frequency and can acquire backscatter at multiple spectral frequencies allows the acquisition of spatially and temporarily co-registered multispectral backscatter data offering capabilities for systematic and accurate mapping of the seabed. In contrast to similar R&D efforts in the proposed service different shallow and deep machine learning architectures will be further validated towards the classification of various seabed classes. An additional novelty lies in the optimization of a single classification model which will provide powerful pre-trained models for different sets of seabed nomenclatures. The validation process towards the targeted TRL8 will be intensive against a number of datasets (e.g., USA, Canada, Atlantic coast, Mediterranean, Santorini, Kolumbo) demonstrating in a comprehensive way the applicability and scalability of the proposed cross-cutting service on several application domains and user communities.

2.4. User Requirements for Underwater Services

The user requirements have been initially formed like 'User Stories'. A User Story is an instrument used in Agile software development to capture a description of a software feature from an end-user perspective. The User Story describes the type of user, what they want and why. A User Story is very high level and helps to create a simplified description of a requirement. Usually, a User Story provides in one sentence enough information related to the described product feature, for which the development team can conduct a reasonable work load estimation. Furthermore, the User Story is used in planning meetings to enable the development team to design and implement the product features.

A User Story typically has a predefined structure:

As a <user-type (stakeholder)>, I want to <user-requirement> so that <reason>

Id	End-User	User-requirement	Reason
R1	All targeted	Upload, store and possibly publish datasets of various formats	To process end-user data with different services and be able to store them and make them available to other users
R2	All targeted	Visualize raw data as well as resulting products and reports	For a first glance, viewing the raw/vendor data (map or mosaic etc.); inspect and evaluate the results
R3	All targeted	To (pre- or post) process the raw data and make any required calibration/corrections (parametrizations)	To correct the data (e.g. image correction/photogrammetrically rectify/sound velocity correct/tide correction etc.)
R4	All targeted	Utilize high-computing power and ensure high-bandwidth access to the data	To solve demanding (post-)processing tasks operating on large inputs
R5	All targeted	Produce bathymetric maps, backscatter mosaics, photomosaics, multifrequency-based seabed classification maps and other related products	To perform archaeological, oil & gas, renewable energy, geological, geohazard and insurance related tasks
R6	All targeted	Document the workflow	For quality assurance, traceability, reproducibility and backlogging
R7	All targeted	Export the results in various file formats	Facilitate the exchange of datasets between users
R8	Archaeologist	To produce geospatial products/ maps with adequate precision from interdisciplinary datasets	In order to comprehend archaeological targets in datasets and fulfill archaeological survey requirements
R9	Archaeologist	To have the possibility to review the georeference of a given dataset	To be able to understand the exact location of an archaeological target (such as a shipwreck) as datasets are georeferenced differently
R10	Archaeologist	To achieve very high spatial accuracy in the delivered products (e.g. to the millimeter)	In order for the result (mapping, 3D model) to be used as accurate archaeological documentation

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R11	Archaeologist	To achieve high quality texture on the delivered products	For reconnaissance purposes: in order to be able to distinguish archaeological targets (shipwrecks from rocks, etc)
R12	Oil, Gas and Renewable Energy Engineer	Classify the seabed type	For the development of the design and installation of submerged tubes and transmission cables, the route design of the transmissioning cable and the appropriate selection of the submarine cable type
R13	Marine Geologist	Classify the seabed type and structure	To assess geohazards and study geological phenomena
R14	Robotics & Computer Vision Engineer	Plan AUV/ROV trajectories	For better AUV/ROV navigation as it is based on GPS, DVL and USBL/LBL information and often not accurate enough to be used right away for bathymetric or photogrammetric post processing

Then the aforementioned user stories/ requirements were linked with a level of priority and value based on end-user recommendations. Also, the manner to confirm their acceptance was also marked down.

Id	Priority	Value	Acceptance
R1	High	High	User Interface (UI) provides functionalities for uploading /downloading data, relying on a Data Transfer Service
R2	Medium	High	UI provides functionalities to visualize the data and the results
R3	High	High	The UI will support manual processing and apply suitable corrections to the data via graphical tools
R4	High	High	Data will be accessible from physically proximal locations and the developed algorithms will allow when required parallel processing and exploitation of any available GPGPU resources
R5	High	High	Implement thematic services that either as stand-alone or in combination produce the required final products
R6	Medium	High	Provide proper support to the logging, backloging, auditing and accounting functionalities offered by the core services
R7	Low	Medium	Implement data serialization processes supporting several widely-used data formats. Rely on a Data Transfer Service for storing and publishing.
R8	Medium	Medium	Provide detailed reporting and evaluation information to assess the quality of the produced results
R9	Low	Medium	Implement Georeference ¹ related data inspection and quality assurance mechanisms
R10	Medium	Medium	Provide detailed reporting and evaluation information to assess the quality of the produced results
R11	Medium	Medium	Rely on interactive visualization methods/services for quality assurance
R12	High	High	The service will be able to produce the classified seabed map

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R13	Medium	High	The service will be able to produce the classified sea as well as geomorphological features when appropriate
R14	Medium	Medium	The service will be able to deliver photomosaics which will aid underwater navigation tasks

Table 2: Summary of the User Requirements for Underwater services

Requirement			Ranking
Req#	Requirement	Type of Requirement (Computing / Storage / Cloud/ etc.)	Mandatory, Convenient, Optional
R01	Upload, store and possibly publish datasets of various formats	Storage	Mandatory
R02	Visualize raw data, resulting products and reports	Functional	Mandatory
		Functional	Convenient
R03	To (pre- or post) process the raw data and make any required calibration / corrections	Computing	Convenient
		Computing	Optional
R04	Utilize high-computing power and ensure high-bandwidth access to the data	Computing	Convenient
		Storage	Convenient
		Cloud	Optional
R05	Produce bathymetric maps, backscatter mosaics, photomosaics, multifrequency-based seabed classification maps and other related products	Computing	Mandatory
		Computing	Mandatory
		Computing	Mandatory
R06	Document the workflow	Cloud	Mandatory
		Cloud	Convenient
		Storage	Mandatory
R07	Export the results in various file formats	Functional	Optional
		Storage	Mandatory
R08	To produce geospatial products/ maps with adequate precision from interdisciplinary datasets	Quality	Mandatory
		Quality	Mandatory
R09	To have the possibility to review the geo-reference of a given dataset	Functional	Convenient
		Quality	Convenient
R10	To achieve very high spatial accuracy in the delivered products	Quality	Mandatory
		Quality	Mandatory
R11	To achieve high quality texture on the delivered products	Quality	Mandatory
		Quality	Convenient
R12	Classify the seabed type	Computing	Mandatory
		Functional	Convenient
R13	Classify the seabed type and structure	Computing	Mandatory
		Functional	Convenient
R14	Plan AUV/ROV trajectories	Functional	Mandatory
		Functional	Convenient

3. User Requirements validation

The end-users community of maritime and underwater archaeologists represented by AMU tested the three services, with a different degree of knowledge on every service, having more practical experience in using UW-MOS (photomosaicking).

3.1. Methodology

A series of trials and workshops were organised with different groups of end-users in order to test the 2nd release of the services (UW-MOS and UW-MAP) as well as intermediate steps and validate the requirements that were initially set, especially R01-R11. At this stage, the Service UW-BAT was not tested, due to technical reasons to be solved in due time.

The trials and workshops were mainly conducted using new material and databases as they have been produced in the framework of different projects conducted by team members of NEANIAS, students and young researchers, as stated above. Moreover, we invited and welcomed the use of databases of colleagues (archaeologists, geologists, hydraulic engineers) working on many different and varied projects, to ensure that a great variety of databases are tested for the validation of the services' requirements.

Below, we will firstly present a series of workshops and dissemination actions organised by AMU, the main end user of NEANIAS representing the maritime and underwater archaeological community, in order to present the framework of trials after the second release of the services with the aim to check if the requirements and the specifications we had set were met and how their ranking has been evolved and redefined. Besides these workshops and trials, a series of dissemination activities, as presented below, gave the opportunity for the presentation of the 2nd release of services and the discussion of the preliminary results as well as the progress of the underwater services development within the international community.

For the results, redefinition of recommendations and discussion of all end-user trials and evaluation tests, please see below at section 3.2.2.

3.1.1. Trials, Workshops and Dissemination activities organised by AMU for the evaluation of the requirements and specifications after the 2nd release of the underwater services

- Calibration tests, Workshop underwater: Aigina, August 2021

This workshop was organized during the 2021 mission of the Aigina Harbour city project. The objective was to test the user requirements R01 to R03 on the UW-MOS services and more specifically the function of the required calibration of the photos as derived by different underwater cameras.

For this purpose, during this workshop, a laminated chess-board was attached to a plexiglass tablet and was placed in the underwater environment inside the trench TR5 of the archaeological excavation located at the fortification wall of the entrance of the ancient naval harbour of Aigina dating to the

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Classical period. The chessboard was photographed by underwater archaeologists, PhD and Master students of MoMArch (Master of Maritime and Coastal Archaeology) using three different underwater cameras with different calibration parameters on the UW-MOS service. The cameras included a wide-angle GoPro HERO 9 Black, a Nikon D5 and a Sony DSC-RX100.

A series of the underwater images were launched on the service immediately on the field site; other datasets were launched after our return to the CNRS Laboratory of AMU in September and October 2021, and finally a workshop was organised in November 2021 for the testing of the service by the students of the two promotions of the Master of Maritime and Coastal Archaeology (MoMArch). At this workshop, external colleagues were invited, as well as underwater archaeologists from CNRS Laboratories and Museum curators (National Museum of Denmark).

Figure 23: Testing requirements of UW-MOS. Underwater photography of the chessboard inside the archaeological excavation trench at the entrance of the naval harbour of the ancient harbour-city of Aigina. @Ministry of Culture, EUA / Aix-Marseille Université – CCJ – MoMArch / EFA, photo : K. Baika (CCJ-AMU) 2021.

- **Dissemination activity: September 2021**

The requirements R01-R03 were met with success, and the first results of the calibration tests that were performed during the August 2021 workshop, and were processed during the fieldwork period, were presented in a dissemination workshop organised in September 2021 in Aigina island. The workshop also comprised the presentation of the NEANIAS Project, its objectives and preliminary results of the 1st and the 2nd release of the services at the local community and local authorities, mainly the official representatives of the Municipality of Aigina and of the Port Authorities of Aigina. It must be noted that the underwater databases of the various photogrammetries conducted in the framework of the Aigina Harbour-City Project (2019-2023) have been used experimentally for the testing of the services since 2020. Therefore, this was a great opportunity to present to the local

community and authorities the opportunities the NEANIAS Project has offered so far to the treatment and analysis of the underwater data of the archaeological site, as well as the future potential.

Participants: Due to Covid-19 restrictions, the workshop was limited to the local authorities, students, local archaeologists from the Ephorate of Antiquities, as well as colleagues from the Archaeological Museum of Aegina. Topographers and architects from local small private companies were also invited. Finally, representatives from the local diving centres and Underwater Works companies were also present.

Figure 24: Presentation of the NEANIAS H2020 Project and its EOSC services to the Municipality and Port Authorities of the island city of Aegina (September 2021)

Figure 24, Presentation of the NEANIAS H2020 Project and its EOSC services to the Municipality and Port Authorities of the island city of Aegina, where scientific research is conducted by the NEANIAS team members and underwater databases are tested on the NEANIAS services. Aigina Harbour-city Project 2021 @ Hellenic Ministry of Culture - EUA / Aix-Marseille Université – CCJ – MoMArch / EFA. Photos: Lionel Roux (CCJ- CNRS- AMU) 2021

- **CNRS Workshop: October 2021**

A third workshop was organized after the return to the CNRS Laboratory as all Aigina mission 2021 databases were treated on both NEANIAS 2nd release UW-MOS Service, as well as @Agisoft software for comparative reasons. The objective was to test all user requirements concerning UW-MOS service, from R03 to R07 and all were met with success. Users were asked to validate especially requirements R01 to R07.

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The workshop was organised by the AMU NEANIAS team members, Master students of maritime and underwater archaeology and CNRS colleagues (photogrameters, topographers and underwater photographers).

Error! Reference source not found., underwater photomosaicking databases from Aigina Harbournity mission 2021 – Location of the underwater research and excavation trenches. Entrance of ancient naval harbour delimited by rectangular towers @Ministry of Culture, EUA / Aix-Marseille Université – CCJ – MoMArch / EFA, drone photo : J. Anbar (AMU, MoMArch – NKUA) 2021.

- **Workshop on 2nd release of services U2, U3: Aix-Marseille University, 19 November 2021**

An official workshop was organized at Aix-Marseille University at the 19th November 2021 at the Salle Informatique of the Maison Méditerranéenne des Sciences de l'Homme (MMSH) at Aix-en-Provence. The objective of the workshop was the systematic testing of the 2nd release of Underwater Services UW-MOS and UW-MAP.

Participants included 16 Master MoMArch students and colleagues from AMU, CCJ-CNRS, and the National Museum of Denmark. Evaluation templates (16 for UW-MOS and 12 for UW-MAP) were filled by the participants.

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Figure 25: Workshop at Aix-Marseille University, 19th November 2021. Testing of 2nd release of Services UW-MOS and UW-MAP. Photos @ Philippe Soubias (CCJ-CNRS-AMU)

- **Dissemination Activity: 25-26 November 2021, presentation during MAGS International Conference**

The NEANIAS project objectives, the advantages of the EOSC bases new underwater services, as well as several of the scientific preliminary results from the treatment of the underwater archaeological databases were presented and discussed in the framework of the 2021 Maritime Archaeology Graduate Symposium by NEANIAS team members in 25th and 26th November 2021 (presentation of Jafar Anbar, NEANIAS Team - AMU). The International Conference was organized in a hybrid way (in presence and virtually) by AMU graduate students and Honor Frost scholars and united young researchers and PhD students of maritime archaeology in international level.

Figure 26: Presentation of the new functionalities of the 2nd release of the NEANIAS Services during the MAGS Conference (25-26 November 2021) by the NEANIAS members. Aix-Marseille University, Centre Camille Jullian, MMSH, Salle Paul Février, 25th November 2021, photo@K.Baikā (CCJ-AMU)

- **Dissemination activity: 10th December 2021, Presentation at the UNESCO headquarters, Paris.**

A similar presentation was done on the 10th December 2021 at the UNESCO headquarters in Paris in the framework of an Eastern Mediterranean International Meeting by the NEANIAS member team Jafar Anbar to an international scientific and stakeholders' community from the Eastern Mediterranean. The presentation included the objectives of the NEANIAS project, as well as trials of the EOSC Underwater Services of databases from fieldwork in Syria.

3.2. Requirements evaluation and validation and recommendations

3.2.1. U1_Service requirements evaluation remarks by end-users (underwater archaeological community)

Due to technical reasons, the evaluation of the second release of the Service UW-BAT has been postponed. Therefore, assessment of users' requirements and new recommendations are not available.

3.2.2. U2_Service requirements' evaluation remarks by end-users (underwater archaeological community)

The Second release of the service provides different processing and reconstruction steps for underwater scenes based on optical/image data:

- Calibration of the camera
- Image Un-distortion (New task)
- Image Enhancement (New task)
- Check image data quality
- Create a 2D image mosaic
- Create a 3D model

Two new tasks were added to the service since the 1st release corresponding to the requirements after the first validation report. These tasks are the *image undistortion* and the *image enhancement*. Both tasks are fundamental for underwater 2D mosaicking and 3D reconstruction. The *image undistortion* is very important to increase the precision. The *image enhancement* as well is an essential step to improve the quality of the output images in two levels (Colour and contrast).

Therefore, a series of datasets were selected for the validation tests of the initial users' requirements and specifications, trying to evaluate a variety of underwater conditions and possessing photos of different qualities and resolutions. As already mentioned, several of the datasets were extracted from photogrammetric databases from Aigina Harbour-city Project 2019-2023, a submerged ancient harbour-city in the Aegean Sea lying today in shallow waters (max. depth of the documented structures at max. -3.00- -6.00 m) and projects in the Aegean Sea. Other databases from underwater archaeological projects in the Mediterranean and the Atlantic Ocean provided by colleagues were also used.

Firstly, the underwater photos of each dataset were acquired with four different cameras (GoPro HERO 9 Black - GoPro HERO 7 Black, Nikon D5 and Sony DSC-RX100) in JPEG format. The sea conditions

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were also different presenting various challenges: Presence or not of strong or medium sun reflections, occasional shadows, good or bad visibility and various depths (always in shallow waters). On the selection of the databases, one of the first technical issues that was tackled in this second release was the limitation of the number of the photos to be uploaded. After continuous discussions with the Coronis colleagues, we were able to upload large datasets concerning the size and the number of the photos. This was a big success made possible with the immigration of the service from a desktop instance to the cloud.

Generally, even from the first release, the U2 service offers a friendly environment even for the end-users of all scientific communities with no previous experience. The documentation is detailed, explanatory and it is easy to follow each step of the process. All the steps in the service (that are automatized) were successfully processed in a simple and direct way from the user-ends. As a result, most datasets worked well validating the service and appreciating the development that has been achieved since the first release.

Steps were performed without leading to errors, and each step could be performed straight forwards, without repetition; not only the high-resolution photos now pass the check image data quality process, but medium quality was well. The 2D mosaic and 3D models are now working successfully, though still in a time-consuming mode. The processing time is still long, but this issue is tackled now with efficiency. Indeed, great progress has been achieved in order to handle datasets of very large capacities (see below: Scalability issues).

In the first release, it was reported that while processing datasets coming from a camera of a particularly wide-angle (Gopro HERO 7 Black – Evaluation tests 8 and 9), end-users experienced a series of different technical issues. Neither the calibration of the camera worked (note, however, that the photos of the chessboard were not taken underwater), nor the checking of the image data quality. Due to these failures on the first steps, the 2D mosaic was incorrect and the 3D model didn't work. Therefore, in this second release we tried different calibration data-sets coming from underwater environments and taken with different underwater cameras to further evaluate this step (see Workshop underwater 1) that is fulfilling all initial requirements and is now working with no difficulties.

In general, the service is simple to use with a user-friendly interface; it is easy to follow the steps, upload different datasets and run the tasks. Any end-user with no previous experience can already use it without difficulty. After running all above different data-sets, the service is very positively evaluated and almost all users' requirements have now been met. (cf. Table in 4.4).

Scalability issues

It is worthwhile to note, that during all assessment trials, we identified that UW-MOS service has scalability issues in two different fronts: the size of the input data and the maximum number of concurrent users.

On one hand, the disk size required by a given task does not only consist of the input images uploaded by the user. In fact, the intermediate steps executed to fulfill these tasks generate several intermediate files (e.g., per-image extracted features in the 2D images, the matches between these features among pairs of images, per-image depth maps estimated, etc.). This effectively doubles or even triples the space requirements for executing a given task. Therefore, the machine where we

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execute the task must have enough disk available so as to be able to store all the intermediate information. We ensure this by deploying in machines with large hard drive space available, and limiting the size of the input datasets.

On the other hand, the maximum amount of memory (RAM) required for a given task is directly related to the size of the input data. In fact, at least one of the steps of the 2D mapping pipeline (the map rendering) and one from the 3D pipeline (the texture mapping) require having all images in RAM at the same time. For a dataset of N images of resolution $W \times H$ with 3 color channels of 1 byte per channel, the amount of RAM in bytes is the product of these quantities, that is: $N \times W \times H \times 3$ bytes are required. Of course, this last part is a bottleneck for scalability, as we are limited by the amount of RAM in the machine or set of machines where we finally deploy our service. For this reason, our service tries to adapt the complexity of the input data to the capacity of the machine where the task is being executed. It does so by computing the measure above, checking if it fits within the RAM in that machine, and in case it does not, it scales the input images by a 2^n factor until the input images fit in the virtual memory of the machine.

Finally, regarding the maximum number of concurrent users that can execute the service, we are currently moving UW-MOS to use Kubernetes jobs instead of the current implementation using Celery task queue. By using Kubernetes jobs, we will be able to launch one Kubernetes Job for each user task. With this design, we can fully scale our service to the maximum allowed by the cluster we are deployed.

General assessment of end-users' requirements of U2 Service

Considering all assessment workshops and trials held the period after the 2nd release of the UW-MOS service by a wide community of end-users (underwater archaeology, marine geology and geohazards and the energy sector), in summary these are the main evaluation remarks on the users' requirements. All comments and suggestions were discussed in detailed and in very close cooperation with the development team CORONIS and several issues were tackled immediately:

Assessing the totality of the users' experience in using the service, Service U2 is simple to login and users can select and navigate to the front page and the documentation page with no problems.

In order to assess the requirements of R01 to R03, the visualisation of the raw data and their process, as well as the calibration and correction of data, all steps of the service were evaluated one by one by the different end users. Finally, the requirements of producing photomosaics (R05) and document the flow (R06) were met successfully:

Camera calibration step is user-friendly, simple to navigate and one can select datasets from local storage or from the Nextcloud. Concerning the service configuration, in case of using datasets from the Nextcloud, end-users expressed the need to have more information about the chessboard (Number of squares in X and Y axis and the side length) that is not immediately visible on the screen. This could be achieved by either uploading a photo of the chessboard in the page of this task or by adding the option (*Review selected photos*).

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Moving to the **Tasks list page** after the submission of the datasets, it is again clear and simple to navigate and discover the different options to download, view the results and share them to Nextcloud. The only issue to solve is that without updating the tasks status, the task will keep pending. It was thus suggested that this step could be performed automatically in the platform.

Image Un-distortion: It is user friendly, simple to navigate and select datasets from local storage or from the Nextcloud. In the service configuration, there is a need to add the option of: Select the calibration file from the Nextcloud.

On the other hand, for the Undistortion scale parameter, ranging from 0 to 1, users expressed that it would be useful to put more information about it in the documentation page. In the tasks list, the Image Undistortion is very simple for the users and well combined with more information for each action. During a workshop that we ran, the process blocked several times before it worked. After having used datasets from local storage, at the final result it was not clear that there is a difference in the comparison between the original input photos and the undistorted photos.

Figure 27: End-users workshop of 21st of November 2021: Screenshots demonstrate issues we faced during and after the test of the Undistortion task was completed.

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Figure 28: Underwater Workshop Aegina mission 2021 and treatment of data in October 2021 CNRS workshop

Figure 28 Workshop during Aigina mission 2021 and treatment of data in October 2021 CNRS workshop: Screenshots show the comparison between original input and the undistorted images of chessboard that were taken by Master MoMArch students during the underwater fieldwork mission of Aigina 2021 – @Aigina Harbour City Project 2019-2023.

Figure 29: End-users' workshop of 21st of November 2021: Treatment of the undistorted images of a chessboard (downloaded from the NextCloud). Photos @ Philippe Soubias (CCJ-AMU)

Image Enhancement: It is a user-friendly, simple to navigate and select datasets from local storage or from the Nextcloud. In the tasks list, the *Image Enhancement* is very simple for the users and well combined with more information provided for each action. The results are very good as it is demonstrated at the images below:

Figure 30: Workshop Aigina mission 2021 and treatment of data in October 2021 during CNRS workshop

Figure 30: Workshop Aigina mission 2021 and treatment of data in October 2021 CNRS workshop: Screenshots show the comparison between original input and enhanced images during the test of the enhancement task.

Check image data quality: During this task, it is simple and user-friendly to select the input images from a local storage or from the Nextcloud. It is clear in the tasks list how to read the report on the quality of the data and this corresponds to the final results in the 2D mosaicking and the 3D reconstruction.

2D mosaicking: This task is user-friendly, simple to navigate and select datasets from local storage or from the Nextcloud. In the service configuration, it is easy as well to select a camera calibration file from a local storage. However, it would be also preferable to add an option to get it from the Nextcloud. Finally, it would be useful to add the option *Georeference the map*, as in the *3D reconstruction* task.

Other remarks concern **operability:** During uploading the photos on the service, it is useful to have the option *uploading panels* to monitor the process and as well to have the *cancellation* option. In the tasks list, it would be preferable to open the *execution report* in a new window directly.

3D reconstruction: The task is user friendly, simple to navigate and select datasets from local storage or from the Nextcloud. In the service configuration, it is easy to select a camera calibration file from a local storage. However, as commented in the *2D reconstruction* task, it would be preferable to add an option to get it from the Nextcloud. The option *Georeference the map* is added as well to the service corresponding to end-users requirement R09. Finally, very big datasets ran with success and we observed high quality texture on the delivered products, that met well the requirement (R11).

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Figure 31: October 2021 CNRS workshop: Screenshots show some problems we faced during uploading the photos for a 3D reconstruction task

However, in some cases we experienced difficulties. For example, during one of the tests of a 3D reconstruction of Shipshed Row 9 in the shipsheds complex of the naval harbour in the harbour-city of Aigina, the reconstructed 3D model was completed successfully, but without texture. The model was imported to MeshLab and 3ds Max softwares, as shown below.

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Figure 32: October 2021 AMU-CNRS workshop: Screenshots shows issues concerning the exported model without texture in the two softwares (MeshLab and 3dsMax)

In the tasks list: Sometimes, the *Delete* button works successfully, but sometimes it leads to an *error page* instead of deleting the tasks. The issue was tackled immediately by the development team and was solved.

Finally, a suggestion of end-users concerns **documentation and description for each task** that could be added with a small *help button* just opposite every toolbar conveying when clicked upon the documentation text available. This would save time and energy, as end-users would not have to refer constantly to the documentation folder – at least at the first trial of the UW-MOS service, before they get accustomed to it. This was the only new recommendation from the part of the end users, and more precisely **more documentation material and description of each task (that would be easily accessible in every step).**

General results

As demonstrated in detail, the UW-MOS service fulfilled all the users requirements as set initially. Moreover, it proved to be a simple service to use with a user-friendly interface, and as required easy to follow the steps, upload different datasets and run the tasks successfully. An underwater archaeologist and geologist, as well an energy designer can use it without any difficulty. Therefore, after running all above different data-sets, the service is very positively evaluated and is working with success fulfilling requirements (R01-R11) set by the community of end users. Only some very minor technical issues are to be considered in the next release, such as ability to handle databases of bigger capacities, and steps that are not always working with specific datasets. All these issues have been

discussed with the developers' team within a very fruitful collaboration framework, commonly beneficial for all scientists and technology partners. In the next step, we would also expect more advanced georeferencing (R09-R10) and high-quality texture (R11), as already described in the user-ends requirements (cf. Table in 4.1).

Still the main technical issues that was encountered was the limitation of the number of photos to be uploaded in this 2nd release, an issue already known and addressed in the first release. As already mentioned, a considerable progress has been now achieved (see above, Scalability issues).

For cross-referencing and evaluation, all the databases which were used for the UW-MOS_Service 2nd release validation test, were also been tested in @Agisoft PhotoScan, the most commonly-used software from many scientific communities for this kind of image processing. We were, thus, able to compare the results in several technical issues, such as processing time, resolution and quality. The UW-MOS service proved to possess several advantages, such as the possibility to run different tasks at the same time, and not be constrained to follow specific steps, or the possibility to choose the creation of a 2D or 3D model immediately, without the need to pass from a 2D processing of data. All these advantages were highly appreciated.

Finally, we must note that there is an effort in this EOSC service not to give any manual control of the different operations to the end-user, the advantage of this approach being mainly an effort towards simplicity of a complicated process, able to attract many non-experienced users with high-quality data-bases to be automatically processed (and hopefully shared in an open environment).

3.2.3. U3_Service requirements evaluation remarks by end-users (underwater archaeological community)

Testing users' requirements on UW-MAP Service, the overall experience when using g the interface and the whole processing is very user-friendly. During all steps, in order to test requirements R01 to R13, it proved easy to navigate in the login page and review the documentation page, as well as to use and follow the different steps. The results are immediate and clear for the user to visualize and check. The classification results of the geological maps are straight-forward to understand and immediately optically evaluated by a non-experienced user. The classification results are consistent with the bathymetry provided.

The results of all three demo databases were transferred in a QGIS environment for cross-referencing and further study and analysis:

- In the first release of the U3 service, the georeferenced file presented problems in classification when transferred in QGIS (the values and the classes do not correspond). In the second release this problem was solved with success.
- Higher accuracy could be expected in the produced map.

The UW-MAP is undoubtedly a very efficient service to identify the geomorphological and sedimentological features of the seabed. Therefore, it seems that this service will be appropriate and very useful for the recognition of archaeological features, though no adapted database with distinct archaeological structures has yet run to test the service, a challenge for the final release of the service.

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Figure 33: Screenshots shows a comparison between the 3 different classifications. DEMO-Bedford-2017- 3 & 4 & 5 Classes

Figure 34: October 2021 AMU-CNRS workshop: Screenshots of the DEMO-Bedford-2017- 3 & 4 & 5 Classes were transferred in a QGIS environment for cross-referencing and further study and analysis

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Figure 35: October 2021 AMU-CNRS workshop: Screenshots of the DEMO-Bedford-2017- 3 & 4 & 5 Classes shows that high accuracy is needed

Figure 36: AMU End-users workshop of 21st of November 2021: Running and testing Service U3 2nd release. Photos @ Philippe Soubias (CCJ - CNRS - AMU)

During the requirements' validation of the 2nd release of the UW-MAP service, the users of the underwater archaeological community experienced several difficulties when transferring the service results to the QGIS environment for cross-referencing and further study and analysis, summarized in the following:

- First, the georeferenced file presented problems in classification when transferred in QGIS (the values and the classes do not correspond).
- Moreover, by the comparison of the resulting classification maps, especially between the 4-classes maps and the 5-classes maps, we observed distinct differences in the categories of the classified material. For example, the zones of mud sand and urchins, fine mud sand and sand with gravel were attributed to different areas in the maps, when ran in the 4-classes process and in the 5-classes process, and sometimes we are losing the colour classification altogether (mostly in the 5-classes process – we are losing the blue colour and two other categories of materials both become black). Thus, in the final result, the extent of the areas cannot be accurately calculated – especially valuable in monitoring studies on marine environments (with or without archaeological features).

- Furthermore, the colours attributed to different materials did not match when processed in the 4-and 5-classes process (ex. Black colour was attributed to gravel and in the map of the 5-classes process was attributed to gravel and sand with gravel). Therefore, when the map is transferred to a QGIS environment, the different materials cannot be distinguished any more.
- Finally, higher image resolution could be expected on the map produced in the next release.

Based on this end-user feedback, already at the second version of the UW-MAP service, the issues regarding visualization and interpretation of the classification maps in GIS environments (and especially QGIS) have been successfully resolved.

During this assessment, it was moreover confirmed that requirements R12 and R13, that concern the classification of the seabed type and structure, as well as R11, concerning the high-quality texture have been met with success. Finally, R09 and R10 concerning georeference and high spatial accuracy have progressed and will be further developed at the 3rd release.

3.3. User Requirements Level of Priority, Value and Acceptance

This section presents the specifications for the underwater services in view of the requirements communicated by the users in the previous section.

The service requirements have initially been arranged according to their type. Five distinct categories have been recognized, more specifically: **storage, computing, cloud, functional and quality requirements**. The first two are related to the access and usage of storage and computing resources by the services. Cloud requirements rely on the features of the cloud infrastructure which will host the service while functional requirements regard specific features to be made available from the services. The quality requirements are necessary for assessing the quality of the services' results.

Another significant aspect while co-designing the specifications of the underwater services is their ranking. This ranking is based on the feasibility and the effort required to satisfy the requirement in relation to the corresponding value expressed by the users in the Tables presented in Section 2.4. Accordingly, each specification has been described as mandatory, convenient or optional. Convenient specifications are interpreted as to be offered, unless in exceptional cases due to limited effort and/or time constraints.

The following table presents the specifications of the underwater services which have been defined to address the user requirements (Section 2.4). The table presents the description of each requirement, its type and ranking according to the aspects described above, a detailed description of the specifications which have been defined for satisfying the corresponding requirement and, finally, the underwater services which should respect the specification. The specifications S01, S02, S08, S09,

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S10 and S11 have been ranked as “mandatory”, specifications S03, S04, S06, S12, S14 and S15 as “convenient” and specifications S05, S07 and S13 as “optional”.

As the U1 service was not ready at the due date of the 2nd release no U1 service end-user validation trials and dissemination actions have been performed. Hence at the time the U2 and U3 services performed the end-user trials no specification and requirements could be retrieved from the end-users to improve the U1 service based on the end-user feedback.

3Table: Requirements – Specifications of Underwater services

Requirement			Ranking	Specifications		
Req#	Requirement	Type of Req (Computing / Storage / Cloud/ etc.)	Mandatory / Convenient / Optional /	Spec #	Description of the required functionalities, software specification	Addressed by the Underwater Service
R01	Upload, store and possibly publish datasets of various formats	Storage	Mandatory	S01	Interface with suitable Data Transfer NEANIAS/EOSC services for uploading / downloading data to medium / long storage locations through well-known protocols (FTP, WebDAV, etc.) and make data FAIR when applicable	U1, U2, U3
R02	Visualize raw data, resulting products and reports	Functional	Mandatory	S02	Each Underwater service implements task-specific reporting mechanisms	U1, U2, U3
		Functional	Convenient	S03	Interface with NEANIAS visualization services for visualizing raw data and results	U1, U2, U3
R03	To (pre- or post) process the raw data and make any required calibration / corrections	Computing	Convenient	S04	Implement customizable, parametrized pipelines for pre- and post-processing the raw data	U1, U2, U3
		Computing	Optional	S05	Interface with external services for task-specific processing	U1, U2, U3
R04	Utilize high-computing power and ensure high-bandwidth access to the data	Computing	Convenient	S06	Design and develop core services based on parallel computing and/or using GPGPU infrastructure	U1, U2, U3
		Storage	Convenient	S01	Interface with a NEANIAS data storage service for transferring data to a physically proximal location for ensuring high-bandwidth access during processing	U1, U2, U3
		Cloud	Optional	S07	Interface with core NEANIAS services during service instantiation for requesting suitable computational resources	U1, U2, U3
R05	Produce bathymetric maps, backscatter mosaics, photomosaics, multifrequency-based seabed classification maps and other related products	Computing	Mandatory	S08	Produce bathymetric maps and backscatter mosaics from multibeam echosounders.	U1
		Computing	Mandatory	S09	Produce photomosaics and 3D models from underwater image datasets	U2
		Computing	Mandatory	S10	Produce multifrequency-based seabed classification maps from multi-dimensional data	U3
R06	Document the workflow	Cloud	Mandatory	S11	Underwater services implement suitable logging mechanisms and store meta-data describing the service parametrization	U1, U2, U3
		Cloud	Convenient	S12	Interface with AAI, auditing and other relevant NEANIAS services for collecting user-related information	U1, U2, U3
		Storage	Mandatory	S01	Interface with NEANIAS data transfer and other relevant services for storing and publishing logs and the workflow related meta-data	U1, U2, U3
R07	Export the results in various file formats	Functional	Optional	S13	Each service offers option to serialize the produced data in widely used file formats	U1, U2, U3
		Storage	Mandatory	S01	Interfaces with NEANIAS data transfer services for storing the output data on suitable storage locations	U1, U2, U3
R08	To produce geospatial products/ maps with adequate precision from interdisciplinary datasets	Quality	Mandatory	S09	Produce photomosaics and 3D models from underwater image datasets	U2
		Quality	Mandatory	S02	Provide through the reporting mechanism suitable evaluation metrics for assessing the quality of the products (at least for the provided demo data)	U1, U2, U3

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R09	To have the possibility to review the geo-reference of a given dataset	Functional	Convenient	S14	Provide textual feedback in the UI summarizing geo-reference of the data	U1, U2, U3
		Quality	Convenient	S03	Interface with NEANIAS visualization services for visual feedback on the geo-reference of the data	U1, U2, U3
R10	To achieve very high spatial accuracy in the delivered products	Quality	Mandatory	S09	Produce photomosaics and 3D models from underwater image datasets	U2
		Quality	Mandatory	S02	Provide through the reporting mechanism suitable evaluation metrics for assessing the quality of the products	U1, U2, U3
R11	To achieve high quality texture on the delivered products	Quality	Mandatory	S02	Provide through the reporting mechanism suitable evaluation metrics for assessing the quality of the products	U1, U2, U3
		Quality	Convenient	S03	Interface with NEANIAS visualization services for visually assessing the quality of the products	U1, U2, U3
R12	Classify the seabed type	Computing	Mandatory	S10	Produce multifrequency-based seabed classification maps from multi-dimensional data capturing different seabed soil types (e.g. rock, mud, sand, clay, etc.)	U3
		Functional	Convenient	S03	Interface with NEANIAS visualization services for visualizing the produced maps	U1, U2, U3
R13	Classify the seabed type and structure	Computing	Mandatory	S10	Produce multifrequency-based seabed classification maps along with any possible geomorphological information	U3
		Functional	Convenient	S03	Interface with NEANIAS visualization services for visualizing the produced maps	U1, U2, U3
R14	Plan AUV/ROV trajectories	Functional	Mandatory	S08	Produce bathymetric maps and backscatter mosaics from multibeam echosounders.	U1
		Functional	Convenient	S15	Aid the navigation of underwater agents by providing spatially accurate photomosaics	U2

4. Software Development Plan and Guidance

4.1. NEANIAS Underwater Services Architecture

In general, the software and service development cycle of the underwater services will closely observe the recommendations and guidelines developed in the context of WP7 (see deliverable D7.1 for details). Moreover, regarding the aspects of service instantiation, registration to the service catalogue and integration to EOSC, the processes defined within WP6 will be followed.

As it is also detailed in D2.6 the software development plans for the 3rd release are as follows:

Table 4: Upcoming 3rd software release

Short name	Sector ¹	Lead ²	TRL ³	Version ⁴	Core Integration ⁵	Documentation Status ⁶	Testing Status ⁷	EOSC Reg. Status ⁸
UW-BAT	Underwater(U1)	TELEDYNE	TRL8	2.0.0	AAI, Logging, Data Sharing Accounting	ready In progress	Always testing	no
UW-MOS	Underwater(U2)	CORONIS	TRL8	2.0.0	AAI, Logging, Accounting, Data Sharing, NEANIAS common UI template, API	ready	Always testing	yes
UW-MAP	Underwater(U3)	ATHENA	TRL8	2.0.0	AAI, Logging, Accounting, Data Sharing, NEANIAS common UI template	ready	Always testing	yes

4.1.1. [U1] Bathymetry mapping from acoustic data service implementation

U1 Software Development Plan and Guidance

Note that due to the delay in the Release #2 deliverable from U1 this development plan and guidance has not been adapted for any end-user validation feedback.

Software development effort The main effort is a user-friendly version of MB-System inside a Jupyter Notebook for processing of acoustic multibeam data for its 1st release (M12). The focus will be on

- * creating the cloud-based infrastructure to upload data, create a secure and isolated user-space and download the result
- * create a workflow for the user from raw data via filtered cleaning to (pre-)processed raster data (grid)

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<p>Processing Pipeline, Software Inputs and Output</p>	<p>Pipeline:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Data upload and raw data view 2. Post processing, data correction 3. Creating products <p>Inputs: Multibeam raw data</p> <p>Outputs: 3D grids/digital terrain models (DTM), 2D images/mosaics (from bathymetry and backscatter)</p>
<p>User Interface</p>	<p>Main functionalities required:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Upload data 2. Create a secure single/multi-user space for data processing 3. Have a workflow-interface that guides the user step by step through parameters and settings in order to choose filtering & other post processing options 4. (Optional: allow/realize a remote GUI to edit data manually & to do navigation correction for AUV/ROV of recorded bathymetry) 5. Display raw and processed data 6. Download processed data and outputs/products
<p>Software Dependencies/required libraries</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operating System Requirement: Ubuntu 18.04 LTS or 20.04 LTS • MB-System • Jupyter Notebook • GMT 5 • Python 3 • GDAL • NetCDF • Proj

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OTPS (Oregon State University Tide Prediction Software) • Docker
Software Deployment In The Cloud	<p>TELEDYNE is delivering the software in containerized form for easy deployment and re-use; Currently spawned on the GARR k8s OpenStack Cluster. Docker open-source container</p> <p>U1 software package plus libraries and dependencies</p>

4.1.2. [U2] Seafloor mosaicking from optical data service implementation

U2 Software Development Plan and Guidance	
Current state	The UW-MOS (U2) service is deployed at the GARR Kubernetes cluster, available as both a web service and a REST API following the OpenAPI 3 standard.
Software development effort	The main effort towards the next release is on improving stability of the tasks under various ranges of inputs, and adapting the computing requirements to the input data, in a way that allows scaling to more powerful backends depending on the computational requirements of a given dataset (more and larger images require more resources). We will do that by moving our tasks to use Kubernetes jobs instead of the current Celery queues. This new approach will allow spawning the task to a Kubernetes cluster other than the one hosting the web/API interface. We also want to connect data between tasks, so that the output of a task can be used as input to another. Finally, we want to increase the number of user parameters for the 2D and 3D mapping tasks.
Processing Pipeline, Software Inputs and Output	<p>Six different types of tasks are available to the user:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Camera calibration. 2. Image undistortion. 3. Image enhancement. 4. Data quality check. 5. 2D mosaicing. 6. 3D reconstruction. <p>The pipeline for executing each task is as follows:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Upload image set (and, optionally, camera calibration information and/or navigation data). 2. Configure relevant parameters for a task. 3. Submit task execution.

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	<p>4. Monitor task status in tasks list until completion, retrieve or visualize the results once done.</p> <p>Inputs: Images, Navigation data, Camera Calibration Data</p> <p>Outputs: processed images, data quality report, 2D images/mosaics or 3D models.</p>
User Interface	<p>The web UI is mainly composed of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A task configuration page for each task, allowing the user to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Upload data from local storage or from the NEANIAS data sharing service (Nextcloud). o Set up parameters relevant to the task. • A list of tasks executed by the user, comprising: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o The starting time and status of each task spawned by the user. o For completed tasks, it allows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Displaying input and processed data. ▪ Downloading the results/products of the task in different formats. ▪ Sharing the results with the user via the NEANIAS data sharing service. ▪ Retrieving a report on the execution of the task, containing the different steps and software versions involved to generate the results provided (focusing on repeatability). ▪ Accessing a user feedback survey. ▪ Deleting the task.
Software Dependencies/required libraries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operating System: Ubuntu 18.04 LTS • OpenCV • OPENMVG • OPENMVS
Software Deployment in the Cloud	<p>The service is already deployed at the GARR Kubernetes cluster.</p>

4.1.3. [U3] Seabed classification from multispectral, multibeam data service implementation

U3 Service - UW-MAP	
Current state	The U3 service is already deployed on the GARR kubernetes cluster. Has been already validated for the datasets presented
Software development effort (next year)	The main efforts will be concentrated on the testing and validation of the developed API that offers UW-MAP functionality to other NEANIAS services, on the addition of the model training pipeline, as well as on improvements in the user interface of the service.
Processing Pipeline, Software Inputs and Output	<p>Pipeline:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Data preprocessing 2) Training 3) Inference <p>Inputs: Multispectral, multibeam data containing different multibeam frequencies in a single multi-channel raster file Outputs: 2D raster file where each pixel contains a label that indicates the seafloor type/ class</p>
User Interface	<p>Main Functionalities required:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data selection or upload • Visualize raw data • Select inference and class nomenclature • Visualize result/ map • Download result/ map
Software Dependencies/ required libraries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • rasterio • NumPy, SciPy • scikit-image • scikit-learn • PyTorch •
Software Deployment in the Cloud	ATHENA and NTUA have already deployed the UW-MAP service on the GARR kubernetes cluster.

5. Conclusions and Future Steps

This deliverable presented the updated requirements of the NEANIAS WP2 “Underwater Research Services” including a detailed description of the user communities, datasets and products involved as well as the technological details of the tools in use and the foreseen architecture, development plan and validation for the three Underwater services after the second release.

More specifically, this deliverable summarizes and contextualizes the WP2 team effort during the last months for re-defining the services requirements of the end-users' communities for implementing the services of the underwater sector after the 2nd release. These requirements have been identified and assessed in the beginning of the project in order to set the co-design and service specifications for the software development plan on the three innovative EOSC services that NEANIAS will implement (D2.1).

During the trials of the 2nd release, several new goals were re-defined, some specifications have been more focused on specific scientific needs, the interface has been occasionally re-designed and adapted for being even more user-friendly and automatized for all levels of end-users encompassing all underwater communities. Comments, suggestions and remarks from external advisors have advanced greatly our initial concept and implementation prospects, have offered ideas for simpler solutions, while at the same time the technical background of all services has been reinforced to withstand bigger capacities for the treatment of considerable underwater datasets.

Moreover, a wider public, experts and professionals from different backgrounds have now contributed by expressing a variety of different end-user's experiences, validating the quality performance and scientific value of the expected results, when using the NEANIAS EOSC novel services.

Towards this effort, invaluable was the contribution of the end-users' partners of NEANIAS that helped greatly by providing unpublished new databases, namely data from underwater archaeological research, environmental and marine surveys, as well as big development projects of the renewable energy companies. All these new datasets, provided valuable feedback in the second release of the NEANIAS innovative services, and will be very useful towards the final step of our project.

The continuous interdisciplinary fruitful discussion between the WP2 team the last months was boosted by the external feedback of end-users, that resulted in overcoming specific issues of capability and operability, and reaching even more specific targets in order to fulfil demanding scientific tasks. However, the NEANIAS EOSC novel underwater services were fundamentally designed to address the requirements of a broader end-user's community, that share common needs, as far as the analysis and the documentation of the sea-bed morphology, classification and photomosaicking is concerned. Therefore, the specified requirements are fundamental regardless of the individual objectives of each research and underwater survey: From ocean circulation, to environmental issues and underwater geohazards to the promotion of underwater cultural heritage to cable and pipe routing and oil and gas exploration, all user-end communities share the same or equivalent requirements from the NEANIAS underwater software services.

This target has been now achieved as this has been demonstrated in the trials of the 2nd release. The NEANIAS EOSC services, currently under implementation for the final release, have demonstrated their potential of being useful, if not indispensable, to a great majority of the scientific underwater

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community internationally, regardless of different scientific goals and approaches for specific final results and products. Underwater archaeologists, marine geologists, environmental scientists and energy developers share common requirements regarding the services to be developed, as the analysis of the user requirements revealed. Therefore, through this task we were able to reach one of the goals of our work, and demonstrate the applicability of the new cross-cutting services for diverse user-communities.

The future steps are already defined by redefining of the required functionalities and the corresponding software development plan needed for each service. The next steps continue with the work towards the final release of the services, followed by the final evaluation and assessment by the end-user community and the external advisors.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
PI	Principal Investigator (a researcher, an engineer, a manager...)
UCH	Underwater Cultural Heritage
AUV	Autonomous Underwater Vehicle
ROV	Remote Operated Vehicle
HVCD link	High Voltage Direct Current
MBES	Multi-Beam Echo-Sounder
MB-System	(Multi-beam) system (Software package)
DTM	Digital Terrain Model
RMS	Reconnaissance Marine Survey